

Highlights

Dual-driven path elimination for vehicle routing with idle times and arrival-time consistency

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- A dual-driven technique for infeasible path elimination is introduced.
- The method targets vehicle routing with idle times and arrival-time consistency.
- It integrates infeasibility detection into a branch-and-cut framework.
- Three formulations are proposed: a compact model, an SEC-enhanced formulation, and an IPEC-based model.
- Instances with up to 100 customers and 5 periods are solved to optimality.

Dual-driven path elimination for vehicle routing with idle times and arrival-time consistency

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Abstract

We present a simple dual-driven methodology for generating infeasible path elimination constraints within branch-and-cut algorithms for vehicle routing problems that incorporate idle times and arrival-time consistency requirements. By leveraging dual information from a feasibility-checking subproblem, the approach systematically identifies the combinatorial sources of infeasibility and uses them to generate and strengthen valid inequalities. We apply the method to the Consistent Traveling Salesperson Problem with idling, which enforces temporal consistency across multiple service days while allowing idle time between tasks. This problem, defined by basic routing and synchronization constraints, serves as an ideal case study to demonstrate the method's effectiveness. Computational experiments on a benchmark set of 756 instances, based on multi-period extensions of classical TSPLIB datasets, show that the approach solves 536 instances to proven optimality, including cases with up to 100 customers and a five-day planning horizon, all within a two-hour time limit.

Keywords: exact algorithms, vehicle routing, synchronization, branch-and-cut, path elimination, time consistency

1. Introduction

An *infeasible Path Elimination Constraint (iPEC)* is a valid inequality that is dynamically introduced to exclude combinations of subpaths that are infeasible in any solution due to synchronization constraints, arrival-time consistency, or other problem-specific requirements arising in vehicle routing problems. These constraints play a central role in the bounding phase of branch-and-cut algorithms, where a master problem determines routing decisions while a subproblem verifies feasibility conditions to eliminate inconsistent partial solutions. IPECs are especially valuable when certain conditions are difficult to express linearly or when their explicit modeling would incur significant computational cost. Instead of relying on large penalty constants (the so-called *Big-M* approach), these inequalities provide a more efficient mechanism to rule out subroutes that implicitly violate global constraints, without resorting to more complex or less tractable formulations.

Identifying the elements required to construct an iPEC is not always straightforward. In some cases, this task relies on a feasibility checking module that only reports whether a candidate solution is feasible,

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without revealing the specific cause of infeasibility. As a result, one only knows that the violation stems from the full combination of arcs defining the solution, with no further insight into the structure of the conflict.

Moreover, since iPECs eliminate infeasible solutions by removing a single arc in the sequence responsible for the infeasibility, their effect on the quality of the Linear Programming (LP) relaxation is often weak. For this reason, it is common practice to strengthen such constraints to enhance algorithmic performance. This strengthening may involve identifying minimally infeasible subsets of arcs within the original solution, adding additional arcs to the left-hand side of the constraint, or combining both strategies. To do this effectively, it is essential to understand the underlying combinatorial structure of the arcs involved.

Although narrower in scope than more general frameworks (such as the Combinatorial Benders Cuts approach introduced by Codato and Fischetti [10]), the approach presented in this work provides a tailored and efficient alternative for constructing exact algorithms for a class of vehicle routing problems involving synchronization constraints. Specifically, our methodology targets a practically motivated subclass centered on *operation synchronization*, which introduces complex temporal interdependencies between tasks. It not only enables the effective generation of iPECs, but also provides the necessary tools for their systematic strengthening. We now review the modeling foundations of this class of problems and how they integrate with broader temporal consistency requirements.

1.1. Overview of vehicle routing problems with synchronization

Many practical routing applications feature synchronization constraints that introduce complex interdependencies between tasks. Our methodology targets a specific yet widely applicable class of such problems, centered on operation synchronization. We begin by reviewing its modeling foundations and how it integrates with broader temporal consistency requirements.

Operation synchronization

In many vehicle routing problems, *operation synchronization constraints* arise when two or more tasks, executed by different vehicles, must be temporally coordinated to carry out a joint operation. It represents a practical and increasingly relevant feature in modern logistics, especially in applications involving cooperative handling, transfers, or team-based services. The aim is to ensure that such tasks, although performed on separate routes, occur within a specified *maximum allowed time window width* (as `maxTimeWidth` throughout this paper) to maintain time consistency.

Enforcing operation synchronization in vehicle routing problems, as discussed in Soares et al. [38], usually requires computing customer *arrival times* based on routing decisions. This is commonly achieved through *precedence constraints* that encode conditional relationships, often of the *if-then* type, between arrival time sequences. While these constraints can be linearized, as in the classic Miller-Tucker-Zemlin (MTZ) constraints for the Traveling Salesperson Problem, such formulations often rely on auxiliary variables and large constants. If not carefully calibrated, these constructs may weaken the LP relaxation, especially when routing variables take fractional values, thus shifting the computational burden to the branching phase.

The study of synchronization in vehicle routing problems was first systematically formalized by Drexel [16], who proposed a classification including five types: task, operation, movement, load, and resource synchronization. More recently, Soares et al. [38] revisited this taxonomy and argued for a simplified distinction

between operation synchronization and *movement synchronization*. In this work, we focus exclusively on the former.

In operation synchronization, the core requirement is that the arrival times of two related tasks must lie within a given temporal offset. These tasks are typically associated with different vehicles and routes, yet are logically part of the same operation. Movement synchronization, by contrast, involves the coordinated displacement of vehicles, which is beyond the scope of this study.

A critical modeling issue in this context is the distinction between *locations*, *tasks*, and *operations*. Synchronization constraints often involve multiple tasks at the same location, which requires treating locations and tasks as separate modeling elements. Likewise, operations are understood as abstractions of task pairs that are interdependent. In our framework, any task carried out collaboratively by more than one vehicle is considered part of an operation composed of several tasks.

We formalize an operation, here involving two tasks, as the set $\{i = (c, k), j = (c, k')\}$, where i and j are tasks performed at the same location c , but assigned to different routes k and k' . In our setting, for all practical purposes, operation and location can be treated as equivalent concepts.

Synchronization constraints

The definition of synchronization constraints requires computing the arrival times of tasks, which in our context are represented by continuous variables s_i , where i denotes a task. It is useful to distinguish three types of constraints typically involved in this computation: *lower-bound constraints*, *upper-bound constraints*, and those that combine both.

Consider two tasks $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c', k)$ assigned to the same route k but associated with different locations c and c' . If task i precedes task j in the route, a lower-bound constraint imposes a minimum on the arrival time of task j . This lower bound is defined relative to the arrival time of task i and is determined by a temporal offset t_{ij} , yielding the constraint:

$$s_i + t_{ij} \leq s_j.$$

By contrast, an upper-bound constraint restricts the arrival time of task j relative to task i , leading to:

$$s_i + t_{ij} \geq s_j.$$

Both types of constraints are typically introduced by logical (nonlinear) formulations, e.g., “if task i precedes task j , then ...”, which must be linearized in order to be used in a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) framework.

The literature on vehicle routing has examined the role of idle time (intentional waiting periods between tasks) from multiple modeling perspectives, ranging from its explicit inclusion in the objective function to its treatment as an intrinsic element of the problem definition (see Soares et al. [38] for a comprehensive review). While incorporating idle time typically increases the total service duration (and may require additional constraints to limit route length) it also significantly enhances solution feasibility in the presence of strict arrival-time consistency requirements.

Vehicle routing problems with synchronization can generally be divided into two categories: those that allow idle time and those that do not. In problems that allow it, synchronization is typically enforced using only lower-bound constraints. In contrast, problems that prohibit idle time use a combination of lower- and upper-bound constraints to prevent any temporal slack between tasks.

In this work, we focus exclusively on lower-bound precedence constraints, which are widely used in models that permit idle time to ensure temporal feasibility.

Arrival-time consistency has emerged as a key factor in customer satisfaction, particularly in service-oriented delivery systems where minimizing temporal variability across service days is essential. This requirement is especially critical for companies operating regular delivery schedules, such as food and beverage suppliers, grocery chains, and other retailers, where predictable service times can significantly enhance the customer experience (see Kovacs et al. [26]).

To operationalize this concept, arrival-time consistency is typically enforced by limiting the variability in arrival times associated with synchronized tasks, that is, tasks belonging to the same operation but scheduled on different service days. Consider two such tasks, $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c, k')$, executed on days k and k' for the same customer c , with arrival times s_i and s_j . The temporal offset between them is given by $|s_j - s_i|$. While some studies consider both lower and upper bounds on this offset, in our setting we focus exclusively on imposing a `maxTimeWidth`, i.e., a maximum allowable width for arrival-time variation.

This requirement, combined with the flexibility to insert idle time between consecutive tasks, gives rise to a class of vehicle routing problems with synchronization constraints that we refer to as *vehicle routing problems with idling and arrival-time consistency (VRP-IATC)*.

These problems capture the key temporal dimensions relevant to our study and provide the structural foundation for the proposed methodology. In the next section, we introduce representative problems within this class that satisfy the necessary conditions for its application.

Idle times and arrival-time consistency in vehicle routing problems

Several vehicle routing problems in the literature incorporate synchronization requirements stemming from idle times and arrival-time consistency. In this subsection, we review representative VRP-IATCs that exemplify these temporal features and provide a suitable ground for applying our approach.

A prominent example, and the focus of this work, is the Consistent Traveling Salesperson Problem (ConTSP), chosen for its conceptual clarity and suitability to illustrate the core aspects of our technique. The ConTSP generalizes the Periodic Traveling Salesperson Problem (PTSP) [9], which assigns customers to service days within a fixed horizon. The ConTSP adds temporal consistency in the form of `maxTimeWidth`, requiring customers visited on multiple days to be served at similar times, thus promoting predictability. The goal is to minimize routing cost while maintaining consistent arrivals.

Subramanyam and Gounaris [40, 41] study two variants: ConTSP1, which forbids idling and minimizes travel cost subject to arrival-time deviations, but relies on precedence constraints incompatible with our approach; and ConTSP2, which permits idling and enforces a `maxTimeWidth`, enlarging the solution space. The latter is solved through a decomposition scheme and will serve as the case study in this paper. Díaz-Ríos and Salazar-González [17] further compare four formulations for both CTSP variants, introducing a

multi-commodity flow model that enables efficient Benders decomposition.

A related problem is the *Selective Routing Problem with Synchronization* [36], motivated by telescope scheduling, where multiple sensors must be synchronized. It can be modeled as a periodic Orienteering Problem with strict arrival-time consistency, and is solved via a branch-and-price-and-cut scheme.

The *Consistent Vehicle Routing Problem (ConVRP)* [21] extends the ConTSP to capacitated fleets and driver consistency. Most formulations prohibit idling, though variants such as Goeke et al. [19] allow flexible departures and waiting at customers, solved through column generation. A further extension is the *VRP with Synchronization at Delivery Locations* [37], where idle times are permitted and customers define their own maxTimeWidths; an adaptive large neighborhood search is proposed.

In food distribution, the *Consistent VRP with Time Windows* [30] enforces customer–driver consistency with hard time windows and irregular demand, solved with a heuristic minimizing the number of drivers. Collaboration settings are addressed by the *Collaborative ConVRP with Workload Balance* [32], where multiple providers cooperate under maxTimeWidths constraints, idle times, and workload balance, maximizing coalition profit. Finally, the *Consistent Electric VRP with Backhauls and Charging* [33] involves EV routing with deliveries and pickups under consistency and energy constraints. Idle times are strategically exploited for battery recharging, and the problem is solved using a hybrid ALNS with constraint and quadratic programming components.

These variants illustrate the breadth of VRPs with synchronization, from conceptual models such as the ConTSP to application-driven problems in logistics, astronomy, and electromobility.

1.2. Exact methods for vehicle routing problems with synchronization

This section reviews exact methods developed for solving vehicle routing problems with synchronization constraints, with particular emphasis on those that model idle times and arrival-time consistency, though not exclusively. All such methods, in one way or another, rely on the well-established branch-and-bound paradigm, which supports many exact algorithms for combinatorial optimization problems. As is well known, this technique systematically explores a search tree in which each node corresponds to a subproblem defined by additional constraints that reduce the feasible region. The objective is to decompose the original problem into more tractable instances while pruning portions of the search space that cannot contain optimal solutions. The key ingredients of any branch-and-bound method are a branching strategy, an effective bounding mechanism, and a node selection policy.

We review both general-purpose approaches based on MILP formulations, typically solved by commercial solvers whose core is a branch-and-bound engine, and tailored branch-and-bound algorithms specifically designed for certain classes of synchronization problems.

Direct MILP-based solution methods

A first approach in the development of exact methods for vehicle routing problems with synchronization is to formulate the problem using a compact model that can be directly solved with a MILP solver such

as IBM ILOG CPLEX¹, Gurobi², or SCIP³. These formulations are typically based on extensions of the classical vehicle routing model, enhanced with additional variables and constraints that capture the temporal dependencies between synchronized tasks.

A common modeling strategy involves using MTZ-type constraints to represent the sequence of visits and compute customer arrival times. Although these constraints are linear, they require the introduction of auxiliary variables to model service times and often rely on large constants to enforce conditional validity. If not properly tuned, these constants can significantly degrade the quality of the linear relaxation, thus impairing solver performance.

While this modeling approach offers advantages in terms of simplicity and ease of implementation, it is limited in scalability. The linear relaxations of such formulations are often weak, leading to long solution times even for medium-sized instances. Nevertheless, compact MILP models remain a valuable tool for early-stage model testing and for solving small instances to global optimality. In fact, they are frequently used to provide a complete formal description of the problem, even when heuristic or alternative exact methods are later proposed for large-scale solution. This is the case in works such as Sarasola and Doerner [37], Kovacs et al. [28], Stavropoulou [39], Mancini et al. [32], and Nolz et al. [33], among others, who introduce compact formulations for routing problems with synchronization, but do not develop specific exact algorithms for their resolution. Similarly, the survey by Soares et al. [38] uses compact models as a framework to formally describe a broad family of synchronization based routing problems, without addressing their solution methodology.

Some authors, however, have sought to strengthen these formulations to improve their computational effectiveness. For example, Díaz-Ríos and Salazar-González [17] propose a number of enhancements that significantly improve the quality of the LP relaxation and, consequently, the performance of MILP-based solution algorithms.

From a computational perspective, commercial MILP solvers internally implement branch-and-bound algorithms, branching primarily on the values of the integer (typically arc binary) decision variables. During the bounding phase, these solvers automatically apply various techniques to tighten the linear relaxation, such as general-purpose cutting planes (e.g., Gomory cuts), and employ primal heuristics to quickly find feasible integer solutions. These internal processes are largely transparent to the user but contribute significantly to solver efficiency.

In summary, compact MILP formulations provide a useful formal framework for representing vehicle routing problems with synchronization, and are well suited for solving small instances. However, due to their limited scalability stemming from weak LP relaxations, more advanced methods are often required to tackle larger and more complex problems.

Branch-and-cut strategies

Branch-and-cut algorithms extend the classical branch-and-bound approach by dynamically adding valid inequalities, commonly referred to as cuts, to strengthen the linear relaxation of the problem. These cuts

¹<https://www.ibm.com/products/ilog-cplex-optimization-studio>

²<https://www.gurobi.com/>

³<https://www.scipopt.org/>

exclude fractional regions of the solution space without removing any feasible integer solutions, significantly improving the bounding power of the relaxed model.

Two main categories of cuts are commonly employed. Feasibility cuts are introduced to eliminate fractional solutions that violate structural constraints of the problem, such as subtour elimination, capacity restrictions, or synchronization requirements. In contrast, reinforcement cuts aim to strengthen the formulation by tightening the linear relaxation, regardless of whether they are associated with explicit violations.

The terminology used in the literature to refer to these cutting-plane strategies is not entirely consistent. Some authors reserve the term branch-and-cut for algorithms that incorporate only integrality reinforcement cuts, while approaches involving feasibility cuts, particularly those added dynamically, are referred to as branch-and-benders methods or lazy constraint generation schemes.

In this work, we adopt a unified perspective and refer to all such methods under the umbrella of branch-and-cut, regardless of the nature or purpose of the added cuts.

A traditional approach for deriving problem-specific cuts is to analyze the underlying combinatorial structure and identify valid inequalities accordingly. For relatively simple problems, polyhedral analysis can lead to strong inequalities such as facet-defining cuts (see, e.g., Laporte et al. [29]). However, this becomes impractical as the complexity of the problem increases, particularly in the presence of synchronization constraints.

Alternatively, valid cuts can be derived through decomposition techniques such as Benders decomposition (see, Benders [7]), where master and subproblem variables are separated and cuts are generated based on the dual solution of the subproblem. This approach is especially useful for problems with block structures or naturally decomposable formulations. Moreover, it is effective even when little is known about the subproblem’s structure. For instance, Riera-Ledesma and Salazar-González [35] propose a branch-and-cut algorithm where Benders cuts, derived from an opaque subproblem, are strengthened via left-hand-side rounding. Nevertheless, Benders cuts are often weaker than those obtained through direct combinatorial analysis, as they focus solely on subproblem feasibility without exploiting the structure of the original problem. Their form is typically not known in advance, which makes them difficult to strengthen, and their implementation can be computationally demanding, especially when Big- M constants are required to model feasibility conditions. As noted by Codato and Fischetti [10], “the classical Benders’ approach can be viewed as a tool to accelerate the solution of the LP relaxation, but not to improve its quality”.

A complementary strategy for generating problem-specific cuts is the use of iPECs, which aim to eliminate invalid routes by identifying incompatible subpaths. This technique has been widely adopted and shown to be effective across various routing problems. For instance, Ascheuer et al. [4] apply it to the Asymmetric Traveling Salesperson Problem with Time Windows, Cordeau [11] to the Dial-a-Ride Problem, Luo et al. [31] to a manpower routing problem with synchronization, Alba Martínez et al. [1] to a vehicle routing problem with loading constraints, Subramanyam and Gounaris [40] to the ConTSP1, and Riera-Ledesma and Salazar-González [36] to the Selective Routing Problem with Synchronization.

In many cases, the key challenge is to identify incompatible subpaths and generate cuts that remove the corresponding invalid solutions. These cuts are initially weak, as they typically eliminate only a single arc from the conflicting path. However, in some cases, they can be strengthened by analyzing the subpath’s

structure and adding extra arcs to the inequality’s left-hand side. This strengthening process is essential for improving relaxation quality and, consequently, algorithmic performance. A noteworthy example of this is the work of Ascheuer et al. [4].

Thus, the method consists of two main steps: identifying conflicting subpaths and generating reinforced cuts to eliminate them.

While in some cases the identification of conflicting subpaths is straightforward, such as in the Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problem with Time Windows [4] or the Dial-a-Ride Problem [11], in others, the process can be considerably more complex. For example, Alba Martínez et al. [1] and Iori and Riera-Ledesma [25] explore route-load compatibility in TSP variants with multiple stacks to identify infeasible loading and unloading sequences that induce subpath conflicts. Similarly, Subramanyam and Gounaris [40] detect pairs of routes that violate temporal consistency constraints under the current scheduling plan.

In the context of the Selective Routing Problem with Synchronization, Riera-Ledesma and Salazar-González [36] address infeasibility arising from idle times by solving a dedicated feasibility subproblem. Since the VRP-IATC belongs to the class of problems in which identifying iPECs is particularly challenging, the present work builds upon and formalizes this latter strategy. Specifically, it introduces a systematic framework for detecting conflicting subpaths and generating strengthened iPECs tailored to the structural features of the ConTSP2. The novelty of this approach lies in the identification of conflicting subpaths by leveraging the underlying combinatorial structure revealed in the dual formulation of the temporal consistency verifier subproblem. This dual perspective allows us to isolate violations in a principled manner, leading to the derivation of effective infeasibility cuts.

It is important to emphasize that, despite exploiting the dual of the temporal consistency verifier subproblem, the proposed method is not based on traditional Benders cut generation. Benders cuts are derived directly from the dual but typically do not capture any specific combinatorial structure. In contrast, the key contribution of our approach lies in using the dual formulation to uncover the combinatorial configuration responsible for infeasibility, an aspect that, to the best of our knowledge, has not been previously explored in this context.

From a practical perspective, modern MILP solvers such as CPLEX and Gurobi allow for the implementation of customized branch-and-cut algorithms via user-defined callbacks. These interfaces enable the detection of infeasible fractional solutions during the search process and the dynamic addition of corresponding cuts. This allows users to focus on the design and validation of problem-specific cuts, while delegating branching, node selection, and other internal mechanisms to the solver. The methodology proposed in this work integrates seamlessly into this framework, enabling the rapid development of effective exact algorithms.

In summary, branch-and-cut algorithms combine the structural power of valid inequalities with the flexibility of branching strategies, offering a robust framework to tackle vehicle routing problems with complex constraints such as synchronization and temporal consistency.

Branch-and-price-and-cut strategies

A more advanced class of exact algorithms for vehicle routing problems with synchronization relies on branch-and-price-and-cut techniques (see, e.g., Desrosiers and Lübbecke [13]), which integrate column

generation into a branch-and-bound framework while enabling the dynamic addition of valid inequalities. These methods are particularly well suited for models naturally expressed with an exponential number of variables, each representing a feasible vehicle route.

In this setting, the original problem is reformulated as a set partitioning model, where each decision variable encodes a complete route that satisfies all operational constraints, including capacity limits and time-based requirements. Since enumerating all such routes is computationally prohibitive, variables (columns) are generated dynamically during the solution process by solving a combinatorial pricing subproblem. This subproblem typically takes the form of an Elementary Shortest Path Problem with Resource Constraints or one of its relaxations, such as the Shortest Path Problem with Resource Constraints, which permits cycles, or the *ng*-route relaxation introduced by Baldacci et al. [6].

A key advantage of this approach lies in its ability to incorporate route-based constraints, such as time windows, vehicle capacities, and synchronization, directly within the pricing routine. This embedded handling ensures that only feasible routes are generated, resulting in linear relaxations that are significantly tighter than those obtained via classical arc-flow models with explicit knapsack constraints.

To further strengthen the master problem and improve convergence, these approaches often include the generation of cutting planes, yielding what is commonly referred to as a branch-price-and-cut scheme. Such cuts may include capacity cuts, iPECs, or other valid inequalities derived from the polyhedral structure of the set partitioning formulation. These cuts can be introduced globally at the root node or dynamically during branching after the column generation process.

An illustrative example is provided by Goeke et al. [19], who solve the Consistent Vehicle Routing Problem using a branch-and-price-and-cut framework. Their formulation assigns each column a set of routes over the planning horizon, and synchronization constraints are embedded in the pricing subproblem itself. In contrast, Riera-Ledesma and Salazar-González [36] apply a similar approach to a selective routing problem, where route feasibility is ensured during pricing, but synchronization is addressed at the master level through the use of iPECs and other valid inequalities.

Some authors have explored column generation schemes where time-related variables remain in the master problem. However, this design choice introduces complications: time variables induce linear costs at the nodes of the pricing subproblem, which hinders the use of standard labeling algorithms. To overcome this challenge, Ioachim et al. [23] and Bélanger et al. [8] employ a more sophisticated extended labeling algorithm first introduced by Ioachim et al. [24].

Despite their increased algorithmic and computational complexity, branch-and-price-and-cut methods have proven highly effective for solving large-scale vehicle routing problems. Their success relies on well-designed pricing heuristics, stabilization techniques, and the ability to incorporate problem-specific synchronization constraints, either within the pricing routine or, alternatively, through reinforced master-level inequalities.

Branching on time windows

An alternative strategy explored by several authors for addressing synchronization within MILP-based frameworks is branching on time windows. This technique was originally introduced by Gélinas et al. [22] in

the context of the Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows, where the authors proposed branching on resource (i.e., time) variables instead of using the more conventional arc-based branching schemes.

The core idea is to split the time window of a given customer node into two disjoint subintervals, thereby creating two branches that enforce mutually exclusive service times. This can render certain routes infeasible in each child node, effectively steering the search toward more temporally consistent solutions. Although this strategy is incomplete on its own and typically needs to be complemented with classical arc-based branching to ensure integrality, it is particularly effective when dealing with fractional solutions involving time variables.

This approach generally assumes a discretized time horizon, which is not considered restrictive in most practical settings. Branching is triggered when fractional time values are detected or when a customer node is visited at multiple times across different routes. In such cases, the remaining time window is partitioned into two subintervals, and the current fractional time assignment is forbidden in both child nodes.

Branching on time windows has been successfully applied in studies such as Ioachim et al. [23], Bélanger et al. [8], and Dohn et al. [14], often in combination with column generation frameworks and advanced labeling algorithms.

A prominent example of this technique is the most effective exact algorithm currently available for solving both variants of the ConTSP (the ConTSP1 and ConTSP2): a decomposition-based branch-and-bound method proposed by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41]. This algorithm relaxes the `maxTimeWidth` constraints at the root node and incrementally restores them to their original bounds through a sequence of branching decisions. At each node of the branch-and-bound tree, a Traveling Salesperson Problem with Time Windows (TSPTW) subproblem is solved using the algorithm of Ascheuer et al. [4], which serves both to assess feasibility and to identify effective branching disjunctions. The disjunctions are defined not only over the width but also the position of the time windows, enabling a fine-grained control of the time consistency constraints.

The algorithm demonstrates strong empirical performance, solving to optimality 542 out of 756 benchmark instances of ConTSP1 and 524 out of 756 instances of ConTSP2, each involving up to 100 customers, within a two-hour time limit per instance.

Summarizing, a variety of exact methods have been developed to address vehicle routing problems with synchronization constraints, ranging from direct MILP formulations to sophisticated branch-and-cut and branch-price-and-cut algorithms. Each approach offers distinct advantages depending on the problem structure, size, and type of synchronization involved. While compact formulations remain useful for small instances and theoretical modeling, advanced techniques such as iPECs, decomposition-based cuts, and branching on time variables are indispensable for tackling realistic and large-scale cases. The continuous integration of structural insights, decomposition strategies, and solver capabilities reflects the evolving landscape of exact optimization methods for synchronized routing, and lays the foundation for the novel contributions introduced in the next section.

1.3. Contribution and outline

This paper introduces a novel technique for generating iPECs within branch-and-cut algorithms for a class of vehicle routing problems with operation synchronization, specifically those involving idle times and arrival-time consistency enforced via `maxTimeWidth` constraints, i.e., VRP-IATCs, and for which the feasibility-checking subproblem can be modeled as a linear program with no objective function terms involving arrival times. We show how the dual variables from this subproblem reveal a clear combinatorial structure that identifies the sources of infeasibility. By detecting sequences of conflicting subpaths, we derive effective iPECs for the master problem. Furthermore, this structural insight allows for the systematic strengthening of the resulting inequalities, contributing to significant improvements in algorithmic performance.

We demonstrate the proposed technique through its application to a representative VRP-IATC, the `ConTSP2`. This problem satisfies the required structural conditions and serves as a suitable case study for illustrating both the simplicity and the effectiveness of our method. The `ConTSP2` is governed by basic routing and synchronization constraints, enabling a clear exposition of the approach. Despite this specificity, the proposed dual-driven strategy is highly modular and general: it can be seamlessly integrated into a wide range of VRP-IATCs by incorporating the additional features and constraints specific to each problem variant.

To assess the effective computational impact of the proposed technique, we introduce three formulations of the problem in which the components leading to our approach are progressively incorporated.

The proposed technique has been computationally evaluated on a benchmark set of instances from the literature. The results are promising, showing consistent reductions in optimality gaps and solving times, and demonstrating the ability to handle instances with up to 100 customers and 5 time periods.

In addition to the algorithmic contributions, we provide a comprehensive open-access repository containing all instance-level computational results, including input parameters, optimal and best-known solutions, bounds, detailed solver logs, and cut statistics. This resource is designed to foster reproducibility and serve as a reliable benchmark for future studies on the `ConTSP2`.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the formulation and notation used for the `ConTSP2`. Section 3 presents a numerical example of a feasible solution. Section 4 introduces and analyzes three MILP formulations for the `ConTSP2`, each designed to isolate and assess the impact of specific modeling choices, such as the inclusion of connectivity constraints or the explicit formulation of infeasible path elimination cuts, on algorithmic performance. Section 5 outlines the proposed methodology for identifying and strengthening violated paths. Section 6 describes the procedures used to generate initial feasible solutions and details the separation routines embedded in the exact algorithm. Section 7 reports computational results on a comprehensive benchmark set. Finally, Section 8 concludes the paper and suggests directions for future research.

2. Problem setting

Although the `ConTSP2` is not a novel problem, it provides a clean and expressive setting to illustrate the proposed methodology. In this section, we formally define the `ConTSP2`, which serves as the running

example throughout the paper, and introduce the notation used in the remainder of the text. We describe the input data structure, the graph-based framework used to represent delivery tasks and synchronization constraints, and the conditions that characterize a feasible solution.

2.1. Input parameters

Let C' be a set of n customer locations. Throughout the paper, the terms *location* and *customer* will be used interchangeably to refer to the elements of C' . A single delivery vehicle is responsible for visiting these customers periodically, starting and ending each route at a central depot, denoted by 0. We define C as the set of all locations including the depot, i.e., $C = C' \cup \{0\}$.

Let K be the set of *service days*, where $|K| \geq 2$. A subset $V' \subseteq C' \times K$ of cardinality m defines the set of delivery tasks, specifying which customer is to be visited on which service day. Each task $i \in V'$ is represented as a pair $i = (c, k)$, with $c \in C'$ and $k \in K$, indicating that customer c must be serviced on day k .

To facilitate modeling, we adopt a split-depot representation by distinguishing between a starting depot node 0 and an ending depot node $n + 1$. Accordingly, we define V as the union of the delivery tasks V' with the set of depot-related tasks $(0, k)$ and $(n + 1, k)$ for each $k \in K$:

$$V := V' \cup \{(0, k), (n + 1, k) \mid k \in K\}.$$

For each service day $k \in K$, let $V[k] \subset V$ denote the set of tasks scheduled on day k , defined as:

$$V[k] := \{(c, k) \in V \mid c \in C\}.$$

That is, $V[k]$ contains all tasks assigned to service day k , including both customer and depot-related tasks.

For each location $c \in C$, we define the set $W[c] \subset V$ as the collection of tasks associated with location c :

$$W[c] := \{(c, k) \in V \mid k \in K\}.$$

Each set $W[c]$ thus corresponds to an operation, consisting of all tasks scheduled at location c across different service days.

Let t_{ij} denote the travel time between the locations associated with tasks i and j , for all $i, j \in V$. Each such movement also incurs a travel cost d_{ij} .

Arrival time consistency in the ConTSP2 is enforced through a parameter ω_c defined for each location $c \in C$. This parameter specifies the `maxTimeWidth` within which service must occur at location c across the planning horizon. Specifically, for any two tasks $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c, k')$ in the same operation $W[c]$, scheduled at times \tilde{s}_i and \tilde{s}_j , respectively, the following consistency condition must be satisfied:

$$\tilde{s}_i - \tilde{s}_j \leq \omega_c, \quad i, j \in W[c], \quad c \in C.$$

In the standard ConTSP2 setting, a uniform value of ω_c is assumed for all customer locations $c \in C'$. We denote this common value by ω when referring to customers. In addition, the ConTSP2 introduces a parameter ω_0 that limits the total duration of each route, measured between the starting task $(0, k)$ and the ending task $(n + 1, k)$ for each service day $k \in K$. While some authors treat this constraint separately,

we incorporate it into the same framework by interpreting ω_0 as the `maxTimeWidth` for the depot-related tasks.

In summary, an input instance of the ConTSP2 consists of:

- A set C of customer locations and the depot,
- A set K of service days,
- A set V of tasks,
- Vectors t and d representing travel times and costs,
- A parameter ω_c specifying the `maxTimeWidths` for locations c in C .

2.2. Additional notation

We introduce additional notation to support the formal description of discrete structures and feasible solutions for the ConTSP2.

Two families of directed graphs are used throughout the modeling: $G[k]$, for each service day $k \in K$, and $H[c]$, for each location $c \in C$. The graphs $G[k]$ represent the vehicle's movement on each day, while the graphs $H[c]$ capture the temporal relationships between delivery tasks associated with the same location. These structures are introduced to clearly separate routing from synchronization constraints and to streamline the model formulation.

For each $k \in K$, let $G[k] = (V[k], A[k])$ denote the directed graph representing all possible vehicle routes on service day k all delivery tasks on service day k and trips between them. Define $V'[k] := V[k] \setminus \{(0, k), (n+1, k)\}$ as the set of delivery tasks assigned to day k . The arc set $A[k]$ includes arcs from the departure task $(0, k)$ to each delivery task in $V'[k]$, arcs between every pair of delivery tasks in $V'[k]$, and arcs from each delivery task in $V'[k]$ to the return task $(n+1, k)$.

To simplify notation, we define the complete arc set as $A := \bigcup_{k \in K} A[k]$, and similarly, the overall routing graph as $G = (V, A)$. The sets $V[k]$ and $A[k]$ are mutually disjoint across service days and form a partition of V and A , respectively.

For each location $c \in C$, we define the graph $H[c] = (W[c], B[c])$, where $W[c]$ is the set of tasks associated with location c , as previously defined. The arc set $B[c]$ consists of all directed arcs between tasks in $W[c]$, capturing the synchronization relationships. For the depot ($c = 0$), the set $B[0] := \bigcup_{k, k' \in K} \{(n+1, k), (0, k')\}$ includes arcs linking each end depot task with all start depot tasks.

We define the complete set of synchronization arcs as $B := \bigcup_{c \in C} B[c]$ and the corresponding synchronization graph as $H = (V, B)$. By construction, the arc sets A and B are disjoint, i.e., $A \cap B = \emptyset$.

This separation into two graph families ensures a clean distinction between vehicle routing decisions and time-based consistency constraints.

Given a service day $k \in K$, a path $P \subseteq A[k]$ of length r is a sequence of arcs of the form

$$P = \{(v_1, v_2), \dots, (v_{r-1}, v_r)\}.$$

For convenience, we will denote paths by their ordered list of vertices, i.e., $P = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r)$. In this context, all paths are assumed to be open (i.e., not necessarily forming a cycle) and simple (i.e., without repeated vertices).

2.3. Definition of a feasible solution

A feasible solution to the ConTSP2, as described by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41], consists of planning the execution of delivery tasks across multiple service days in such a way that all routing and temporal consistency constraints are satisfied. This includes respecting the `maxTimeWidths` imposed on tasks associated with the same location. By leveraging the graph structures defined in the previous section, we can describe feasible solutions in terms of routing paths and associated arrival times.

Formally, a feasible solution is defined by two components:

1. A Hamiltonian path $P \subseteq A[k]$ for each service day $k \in K$. Given the structure of the graph $G[k]$, each path P must start at the departure task $(0, k)$, visit all delivery tasks in $V'[k]$, and end at the arrival task $(n + 1, k)$.
2. A vector \tilde{s} of arrival times, indexed over the set of tasks V . For each arc $(i, j) \in P$, the arrival times must satisfy the precedence constraint:

$$\tilde{s}_i + t_{ij} \leq \tilde{s}_j,$$

ensuring the correct ordering of tasks along each route. Additionally, arrival times must satisfy the following synchronization constraint:

$$\tilde{s}_j - \tilde{s}_i \leq \omega_c \quad (i, j) \in B[c], c \in C. \quad (1)$$

That is, for any pair of tasks associated with the same location c , the time difference between their execution must not exceed the `maxTimeWidth`, ω_c , thus enforcing arrival-time consistency across days.

3. Numerical example of a feasible solution

This section presents a numerical example of a feasible solution for the ConTSP2. We consider the test instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`, which belongs to the dataset⁴ proposed by Subramanyam and Gounaris in their studies [40, 41].

Specifically, this instance contains 14 locations, where the first location is the depot, and the remaining 13 locations are customers. The instance considers 3 service days, with a `maxTimeWidth` of $\omega = 617$ for each customer. The maximum service time is set to $\omega_0 = 2817$. Both the transport times t and the arc costs d are derived from the geographical distances between locations, following the TSPLIB95 specifications⁵.

The demands of each location in the set C for each service day in K are summarized in Table 1. Notably, locations c_2 , c_{10} , and c_{11} have no demand on any service day. In contrast, location 0 (the depot) has demand on all service days. Additionally, the customer associated with location c_5 requires service on each of the

⁴<http://gounaris.cheme.cmu.edu/datasets/contsp/>

⁵<http://comopt.ifl.uni-heidelberg.de/software/TSPLIB95/tsp95.pdf>

three service days, while customers at locations c_8 and c_{13} require service on only one day. This demand table indicates that the instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H` contains a total of 19 delivery tasks, in addition to 3 departure and 3 arrival tasks.

Table 1: Demands for each location in set C for each service day, for the instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`.

K	C													
	0	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5	c_6	c_7	c_8	c_9	c_{10}	c_{11}	c_{12}	c_{13}	c_{14}
1	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓		
2	✓		✓		✓			✓	✓			✓		✓
3	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓						✓	✓

Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of a feasible solution for the instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`. The figure includes two subfigures illustrating different aspects of the same schedule. The first subfigure presents the scheduling of delivery tasks across the three service days in K , while the second subfigure displays the same schedule, organized by customer locations in C' .

The scheduling time of each task is represented by a vertical segment, with a label at the bottom indicating its identifier. The number on the left of each row in subfigure 1(a) denotes the corresponding service day. For example, the first vertical segment in row 1 of subfigure 1(a) indicates that delivery task $(c_9, 1)$, associated with customer 9 on service day 1, is scheduled at time 160.

Transitions between tasks are depicted as gray-shaded rectangles, with the transport time between two tasks specified inside.

Additionally, subfigure 1(a) highlights a violet-shaded region preceding task $(c_{12}, 1)$, following task $(c_7, 1)$. This violet area represents a waiting time of 146 units before performing task $(c_{12}, 1)$, after a travel duration of 163 units from task $(c_7, 1)$.

Although Figure 1 does not explicitly display them, each service day k begins with departure task $(0, k)$ and concludes with arrival task $(n + 1, k)$.

Subfigure 1(b) presents the same scheduling information as subfigure 1(a), but organized by customer. This visualization facilitates verification of constraint (1) compliance. A blue-shaded rectangle, centered at the average scheduling time of a customer's tasks, represents the `maxTimeWidth`. This graphical representation confirms that all delivery tasks for a customer meet constraints (1), as they remain within the rectangle's boundaries. Each row's leftmost identifier corresponds to the associated customer.

In subfigure 1(a), on the first day, the vehicle completes its deliveries in 2660 time units, though the route cost is 2514, considering a waiting time of 146 units. On the second service day, the vehicle consumes 2561 time units, and on the third service day, it consumes 2233 time units. None of the routes exceed the defined maximum service time. The total cost of this solution is 7308.

Including waiting times helps achieve feasible solutions by accommodating the `maxTimeWidth` constraint. Consider the tasks $(c_{12}, 1)$ and $(c_{12}, 2)$ in subfigure 1(b). Both tasks are scheduled within the `maxTimeWidth`, allowing the vehicle to wait 146 time units on the first service day before performing task $(c_{12}, 2)$. Without

(a) Timeline representation of delivery tasks across the 3 service days. Each row corresponds to a service day, as indicated on the left.

(b) Timeline representation of delivery tasks organized by customer location. Each row corresponds to a customer, as indicated on the left.

Figure 1: Graphical depiction of a feasible solution for the ConTSP2 instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`. The first subfigure illustrates tasks scheduled per service day, while the second organizes them by customer.

this adjustment, the solution would be infeasible.

However, incorporating waiting times comes at the cost of increasing the total service time. Additionally, imposing the maximum service time constraint ω_0 may result in a solution that is feasible in terms of `max TimeWidth` but infeasible due to exceeding the allowable service duration.

4. Formulations

This section introduces and analyzes three MILP formulations for the ConTSP2, each designed to isolate and assess the impact of specific modeling choices on algorithmic performance. All three formulations build upon the combinatorial description of feasible solutions provided in Section 2.3, which serves as the structural foundation for the modeling approach.

The first model, referred to as the Compact Formulation, encodes the full set of feasibility constraints using a polynomial number of inequalities. In particular, arrival-time consistency is enforced explicitly via time variables, which are used to model synchronization constraints. This model is fully expressible within

off-the-shelf MILP solvers and serves as a natural baseline for evaluating solution quality and computational performance.

The second model, called the SEC-Enhanced Formulation, strengthens the compact model by incorporating classical connectivity constraints, which significantly improve the linear relaxation. As in the compact model, synchronization constraints are modeled through time variables, allowing us to evaluate the effect of standard structural reinforcement techniques without altering the overall modeling approach.

Finally, the Path Elimination Formulation omits the arrival-time variables altogether and replaces the timing and consistency constraints with a family of infeasible path elimination constraints based solely on routing variables. This model leverages structural insights into the problem to generate strong feasibility cuts, and serves as the basis for the dual-driven methodology proposed in this work.

All three formulations are tested and compared in Section 7.2 to evaluate their effectiveness and highlight the performance gains achieved by integrating iPEC-based reasoning. The best-performing formulation is then used in the computational comparison against the state-of-the-art algorithm of Subramanyam and Gounaris [41].

For clarity, we define the following standard notation. Given vertex subsets $S, T \subseteq V$, we let:

$$\begin{aligned} A(S) &:= \{(i, j) \in A \mid i, j \in S\}, \\ A(S : T) &:= \{(i, j) \in A \mid i \in S, j \in T\}, \\ \delta^-(S) &:= \{(i, j) \in A \mid i \in V \setminus S, j \in S\}, \\ \delta^+(S) &:= \{(i, j) \in A \mid i \in S, j \in V \setminus S\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $S = \{i\}$, we use the shorthand $\delta^-(i)$ and $\delta^+(i)$.

We define two families of variables. The first is used in all three models; the second appears only in the first two models:

- For each arc $(i, j) \in A$, the binary variable x_{ij} takes the value 1 if the vehicle performs task j immediately after task i .
- For each task $j \in V$, the continuous variable s_j represents the arrival time at task j .

For any subset of arcs $F \subseteq A$, we write $x(F)$ to denote $\sum_{(i,j) \in F} x_{ij}$.

The first two models, both based on arrival-time variables, include three main components: (i) constraints defining a Hamiltonian path for each service day, (ii) precedence constraints encoding arrival times, and (iii) arrival-time consistency constraints. The path elimination model also incorporates Hamiltonian path constraints but replaces the latter two components with iPECs. Each of the three families of constraints is described in what follows.

Hamiltonian paths

Given the structure of the graph $G = (V, A)$, defined above, the following constraints define $|K|$ Hamiltonian paths, one for each service day, based on the x variables:

$$x(\delta^+(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^- \quad (2)$$

$$x(\delta^-(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^+ \quad (3)$$

$$x(A(S)) \leq |S| - 1 \quad S \subset V, |S| \geq 2 \quad (4)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (i, j) \in A, \quad (5)$$

where $0^- := \{(n+1, k) \mid k \in K\}$ and $0^+ := \{(0, k) \mid k \in K\}$ are the sets of arrival and departure tasks at the depot, respectively. Constraints (2)–(3) ensure that each task is visited exactly once. Constraint (4) prevents cycles in the service path. Constraint (5) enforces the binary nature of the variables x .

Precedence constraints

These constraints determine the arrival times s_j based on a selected path defined by variables x . They can be expressed using logical terms as follows:

$$x_{ij} = 1 \Rightarrow s_i + t_{ij} \leq s_j \quad (i, j) \in A. \quad (6)$$

These logical constraints ensure that if task j follows i , then j starts no earlier than the completion of i plus the travel time between them, for each arc $(i, j) \in A$. They naturally allow for waiting time between tasks.

To linearize these constraints, we apply the standard big- M reformulation:

$$s_i + t_{ij} - M(1 - x_{ij}) \leq s_j \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (7)$$

Here, M is a large constant that effectively deactivates the constraint when $x_{ij} = 0$. These are known as MTZ constraints (see, e.g., Gouveia and Pires [20]). It should be noted that (7) also prevents subtours, making (4) redundant in integer solutions. A valid choice for M is ω_0 , since no s_j can exceed this value due to the maximum service time constraints.

Arrival time consistency constraints

This final group of constraints enforces the arrival time consistency requirements. Specifically, for any pair of deliveries (i, j) to the same customer $c \in C$:

$$s_j - s_i \leq \omega_c \quad (i, j) \in B[c], c \in C. \quad (8)$$

These inequalities ensure that delivery tasks for the same customer occur within the `maxTimeWidth`. They also implicitly enforce the upper bound ω_0 on the total duration of each service day.

4.1. Compact formulation

The compact formulation serves as a baseline model. It captures all relevant constraints using a polynomial number of inequalities and can be directly handled by any commercial MILP solver. This model

combines standard routing constraints with a linearized version of the precedence logic, using big- M coefficients to enforce the correct timing of tasks. In addition, arrival time consistency is enforced by bounding the temporal gap between visits to the same customer.

Despite its structural simplicity and ease of implementation, this model suffers from weak linear relaxations due to the presence of big- M terms. These constraints become particularly ineffective when x variables take fractional values, resulting in poor lower bounds and increased reliance on the branching mechanism. Nevertheless, the compact formulation is useful for analyzing the overall structure of the problem and provides a reference point for evaluating the effectiveness of more advanced models.

$$\min \sum_{(i,j) \in A} d_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (9)$$

subject to:

$$x(\delta^+(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^- \quad (2)$$

$$x(\delta^-(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^+ \quad (3)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (5)$$

$$s_i + t_{ij} - M(1 - x_{ij}) \leq s_j \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (7)$$

$$s_j - s_i \leq \omega_c \quad (i, j) \in B[c], c \in C. \quad (8)$$

The objective function (9) minimizes the total distance traveled. Time variables s_j do not require explicit upper bounds thanks to (8), and initializing $s_{(0,k)} = 0$ for each $k \in K$ is also unnecessary.

4.2. SEC-Enhanced formulation

The SEC-Enhanced formulation builds directly upon the compact model by incorporating a classical family of connectivity constraints, which are added dynamically during the branch-and-bound process. These constraints explicitly eliminate infeasible cycles in the routing structure and provide a significant strengthening of the LP relaxation, especially in early nodes of the search tree.

This enhancement allows for a more accurate assessment of the solution space and reduces the number of nodes required to prove optimality. Although the use of connectivity constraints introduces an exponential number of constraints, their separation is well understood and efficient in practice. This formulation provides an intermediate step between the purely compact representation and the more sophisticated path elimination approach described next.

$$\min \sum_{(i,j) \in A} d_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (9)$$

subject to:

$$x(\delta^+(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^- \quad (2)$$

$$x(\delta^-(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^+ \quad (3)$$

$$x(A(S)) \leq |S| - 1 \quad S \subset V, |S| \geq 2 \quad (4)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (5)$$

$$s_i + t_{ij} - M(1 - x_{ij}) \leq s_j \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (7)$$

$$s_j - s_i \leq \omega_c \quad (i, j) \in B[c], c \in C. \quad (8)$$

Constraints (4) are dynamically added on demand during the solution process to eliminate infeasible cycles and strengthen the LP relaxation.

4.3. Path elimination formulation

The third formulation introduces a qualitative shift in modeling: instead of relying on precedence and timing variables, it enforces feasibility through a family of infeasibility path elimination constraints (iPECs) expressed solely in terms of the routing variables x . These constraints are derived from structural incompatibilities between subpaths that cannot coexist in a feasible solution due to synchronization requirements.

This approach eliminates the need for big- M coefficients and leads to tighter LP relaxations by directly targeting infeasible routing patterns. It forms the core of the dual-driven separation strategy proposed in this work, where infeasibility is identified through subproblem analysis and used to generate strong, problem-specific cuts.

The resulting model preserves the routing structure of the SEC-Enhanced formulation, but replaces timing and consistency constraints with iPECs dynamically added during the solution process. As shown in the computational study, this formulation achieves substantial improvements in both solution times and bounds, especially for larger or more tightly constrained instances.

$$\min \sum_{(i,j) \in A} d_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (9)$$

subject to:

$$x(\delta^+(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^- \quad (2)$$

$$x(\delta^-(j)) = 1 \quad j \in V \setminus 0^+ \quad (3)$$

$$x(A(S)) \leq |S| - 1 \quad S \subset V, |S| \geq 2 \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} x(P) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1 \quad \mathcal{T} \in \mathcal{T} \quad (10)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (i, j) \in A. \quad (5)$$

Constraints (10) remove those combinations of subpaths that lead to infeasibility because of maxTime Width violation. The set \mathcal{T} represents the collection of all sets of mutually incompatible paths, where each $\mathcal{T} \in \mathcal{T}$ denotes a specific subset of paths that are incompatible with each other.

At this point, several questions arise: how can these new inequalities (10) be generated, and how can we ensure they are strong enough to serve as an alternative to the compact model? We address these questions in the next section.

5. Identifying iPECs

To identify iPECs that render any infeasible solution, we outline a methodology in this section. First, we establish a method to determine whether a solution described in terms of variables x is feasible for the ConTSP2. Then, we propose a method to generate inequalities that, based on this feasibility check, help avoid infeasible solutions. Finally, we introduce a third step that reinforces the obtained constraints by tightening them, further improving the formulation's strength.

5.1. Checking feasibility

Consider a solution \tilde{x} obtained from the model (2)–(5) and (9), where the integrality constraints (5) have been relaxed. Additionally, branching constraints imposed on the x variables may be present, as well as some constraints from the family (10) that may have been introduced earlier. The solution \tilde{x} is feasible for the ConTSP2 if there exist values of s satisfying the following constraints:

$$-s_j + \tilde{x}_{ij}s_i \leq -\tilde{x}_{ij}t_{ij} \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (\alpha_{ij}) \quad (11)$$

$$s_j - s_i \leq \omega_c \quad (i, j) \in B[c], c \in C. \quad (\beta_{ij}) \quad (8)$$

Where constraints (11) particularize constraints (6) for the solution \tilde{x} .

To determine whether there exists a vector s satisfying constraints (11) and (8) for a given solution \tilde{x} , we apply duality theory by associating dual variables α and β with the synchronization constraints (11) and the maxTimeWidth constraints (8), respectively. The feasibility of this model is then directly related to the unboundedness of the following dual linear program:

$$\min - \sum_{(i,j) \in A} \tilde{x}_{ij}t_{ij}\alpha_{ij} + \sum_{(i,j) \in B[c], c \in C} \omega_c \beta_{ij} \quad (12)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{(j,i) \in A[k]} \tilde{x}_{ji}\alpha_{ji} - \sum_{(i,j) \in A[k]} \alpha_{ij} =$$

$$\sum_{(j,i) \in B[c]} \beta_{ji} - \sum_{(i,j) \in B[c]} \beta_{ij} \quad j = (c, k) \in V \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (14)$$

$$\beta_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (i, j) \in B. \quad (15)$$

The set of constraints (13) enforces flow conservation at each vertex $j = (c, k)$ in the network $\mathcal{G} = (V, A \cup B)$. Within each temporal layer $A[k]$, for every $k \in K$, flow is driven by the α_{ij} variables over arcs $(i, j) \in A[k]$ that are active in \tilde{x} , while flow across arcs in B is determined by the β_{ij} variables.

Figure 2: Example of a fractional solution containing two paths with value 0.5 from $(0, k)$ to $(n+1, k)$. The first path follows $(0, k) \rightarrow (c_1, k) \rightarrow (c_2, k) \rightarrow (c_4, k) \rightarrow (n+1, k)$, while the second follows $(0, k) \rightarrow (c_1, k) \rightarrow (c_3, k) \rightarrow (c_4, k) \rightarrow (n+1, k)$. Solid arcs indicate edges with $\tilde{x} = 1$, while dashed arcs correspond to edges with $\tilde{x} = 0.5$.

It is important to note that the solution \tilde{x} satisfies constraints (2)–(4), with $0 \leq x_{ij} \leq 1$, for all $(i, j) \in A$. Therefore, for each period $k \in K$, the subgraph induced by arcs in $A[k]$ contains only paths, either integer or fractional, connecting $(0, k)$ to $(n+1, k)$. As a consequence, there are no directed cycles entirely contained within any individual layer $A[k]$ under \tilde{x} .

If a layer $A[k]$ were to contain arcs forming a (fractional) cycle $O \subseteq A[k]$, for instance, due to the presence of two or more overlapping fractional paths in \tilde{x} (e.g., $O = ((c_2, k), (c_3, k)), ((c_3, k), (c_2, k))$), as illustrated in Figure 2), with $\tilde{x}_{ij} < 1$, for $(i, j) \in O$, then the left-hand side of constraint (13) would violate the flow conservation condition for each vertex involved in the cycle. That is, for any task j within the cycle, the corresponding constraint would fail to satisfy

$$\sum_{(j,i) \in O} \tilde{x}_{ji} \alpha_{ji} = \sum_{(i,j) \in O} \alpha_{ij},$$

thereby disrupting the feasibility of a cyclical flow in the dual solution.

Constraints (14) and (15) impose non-negativity on the dual variables α and β , respectively. Note that this dual model is always feasible, as it admits the trivial solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}) = (0, 0)$, although our interest lies in its potential unboundedness as a certificate of primal infeasibility.

In conjunction with the objective function (12), this model determines whether the solution \tilde{x} is feasible for the ConTSP2. The objective function consists of two components: the first one is proportional to the values of \tilde{x} on the selected arcs and to the transition service times between tasks in A , while the second one is proportional to the maxTimeWidth associated with the arcs in B that participate in the cycle.

Practically, the objective function compares the total transition service time across the cycle's arcs in A with the aggregate width of the time windows associated with the arcs in B that complete the cycle. If the transition time exceeds the cumulative time-window allowance, the objective becomes unbounded, signaling infeasibility.

5.2. Generating iPECs

To derive valid infeasible path inequalities from an infeasible solution \tilde{x} , we establish upper bounds on the variables α and β . To this end, we replace constraints (14) and (15) with the following bounds:

$$0 \leq \alpha_{ij} \leq \bar{\alpha} \quad (i, j) \in A \quad (16)$$

$$0 \leq \beta_{ij} \leq \bar{\beta} \quad (i, j) \in B, \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ can take the same value to prevent unbounded solutions. This reformulation ensures that the objective function (12) remains bounded.

We now show that any infeasible solution \tilde{x} to the ConTSP2 gives rise to a sequence of mutually incompatible subpaths. This structural insight serves as the foundation for deriving valid inequalities for the ConTSP2, as well as for developing techniques to strengthen them within an exact solution framework.

Proposition 1. *Let \tilde{x} be any infeasible solution to the ConTSP2. Then, there exists a finite cyclic structure in the network $\mathcal{G} = (V, A \cup B)$, composed of a sequence of subpaths P_1, \dots, P_p , with $p \geq 1$, each associated with a service day and connected by consistency arcs. This structure, referred to as a consistency cycle, is responsible for the violation of the temporal constraints of the problem.*

Proof. Assume that \tilde{x} is an infeasible solution to the ConTSP2. Consider the dual model $D(\tilde{x})$, defined by constraints (13), (16), (17), and objective function (12).

If \tilde{x} is infeasible, then the dual problem attains a strictly negative optimal value, indicating that the total service time across transitions exceeds the permissible cumulative time defined by the consistency windows. Therefore, there exists an optimal dual solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ with non-zero objective value.

Let $\tilde{A} := \{(i, j) \in A \mid \tilde{\alpha}_{ij} > 0\}$ and $\tilde{B} := \{(i, j) \in B \mid \tilde{\beta}_{ij} > 0\}$ denote the support of this solution, and define the corresponding support graph $\tilde{G} = (V, \tilde{A} \cup \tilde{B})$. Since the flow conservation constraints (13) enforce zero net flow at every vertex, each connected component of \tilde{G} must form a closed structure within \mathcal{G} .

Furthermore, as shown in Section 5.1, intra-layer cycles within each $A[k]$ are excluded by construction. Consequently, any closed component in \tilde{G} must necessarily include at least one arc from B , linking subpaths across different service periods.

Two distinct types of consistency cycles may arise:

- A single intra-day path within some layer $A[k]$, closed by an arc $((n+1, k), (0, k)) \in B$, violating the global time window ω_0 .
- A cross-period sequence of subpaths connected by arcs in $B[c]$ for some $c \in C$, resulting in a violation of the inter-period consistency constraint ω_c .

Moreover, if the dual solution is obtained using a vertex-based algorithm such as the Simplex method, it corresponds to an extreme point of the feasible polyhedron. Hence, the connected components of the support graph cannot be expressed as convex combinations of simpler structures; they form minimal, elementary cycles that expose the infeasibility of \tilde{x} .

In summary, each component of the support graph \tilde{G} defines a *consistency cycle*, composed of subpaths joined across days by consistency arcs, whose aggregate service time violates the time consistency conditions of the ConTSP2. This completes the proof. \square

Figure 3: Example of an infeasible partial solution for the instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`, illustrating the values of \tilde{x} and $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ across service days. Transitions included in \tilde{x} are shown as shaded rectangles; arcs corresponding to $\tilde{\alpha}$ are highlighted in blue, and those corresponding to $\tilde{\beta}$ in red.

Figure 4: Graph representation of the values $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ shown in Figure 3, embedded in graph \mathcal{G} .

Figure 3 provides a graphical representation of the structure of the cycles described by $D(\tilde{x})$ through a concrete example. The figure depicts a solution in terms of the α and β variables derived from a single infeasible solution \tilde{x} . The input data corresponds to the instance `burma14_p3_f50_1H`, whose details have been presented in Section 3.

The figure displays the values of \tilde{x} , that is, the transitions between task pairs (i, j) included in solution \tilde{x} , as gray-shaded rectangles. In this particular case, they all correspond to $\tilde{x}_{ij} = 1$, since the infeasible solution \tilde{x} obtained in this iteration is integer. Blue-shaded rectangles similarly represent transitions included in \tilde{x} , highlighting the involved tasks. The transportation time between tasks is shown inside each transition rectangle.

The figure also illustrates the solution values $\tilde{\alpha}$ and $\tilde{\beta}$ from the variables α and β for $D(\tilde{x})$. Blue-shaded rectangles denote transitions with non-zero values of $\tilde{\alpha}$ for task pairs $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c', k)$ where $\tilde{x}_{ij} > 0$, for some $c, c' \in C$ and $k \in K$. Red arcs represent non-zero values of $\tilde{\beta}$ and connect segments from different service days, specifically, tasks $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c, k')$, for some $c \in C$ and $k \neq k' \in K$.

Figure 4 shows the consistency cycle associated with the same $\tilde{\alpha}$ and $\tilde{\beta}$ values from Figure 3, now embedded in the graph \mathcal{G} . In this example, the total transportation time across the arcs in A belonging to the three subpaths equals 4507 time units. Meanwhile, the total time-window allowance across the three arcs in B , which link those subpaths, adds up to 1851 time units. This results in a violation of 2656 time units.

Building on this result, we observe that, for any infeasible solution \tilde{x} to the `ContTSP2`, the set \mathcal{T} of subpaths extracted from the corresponding dual solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ defines a valid inequality of the form:

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} x(P) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1. \quad (18)$$

This inequality eliminates \tilde{x} by explicitly excluding the combination of subpaths that jointly violate the problem's consistency constraints.

The inequality (18) can be explicitly written for example illustrated in Figure 4 as

$$\begin{aligned}
& x_{(c_9,1),(c_7,1)} + x_{(c_7,3),(c_6,3)} + x_{(c_6,3),(c_5,3)} + \\
& \quad x_{(c_5,3),(c_4,3)} + x_{(c_4,3),(c_{14},3)} + x_{(c_{14},2),(c_{12},2)} \\
& \quad \quad \quad + x_{(c_{12},2),(c_5,2)} + x_{(c_5,2),(c_9,2)} \leq 7. \quad (19)
\end{aligned}$$

5.3. Strengthening iPECs

In the previous section, we described how to derive valid iPECs for the ConTSP2 from an infeasible solution \tilde{x} . We now show how these inequalities can be strengthened to enhance their impact on the LP relaxation.

In this section, we present two approaches for reinforcing these inequalities. The first one, known as *lifting*, consists of adding variables to the left-hand side of the inequality to strengthen the LP relaxation. The second approach aims to make the inequality more restrictive by tightening its coefficients. Specifically, it involves identifying a *minimum infeasible subsystem* of the variables appearing in the inequality, which are responsible for its violation. This allows not only for the elimination of the specific infeasible solution that originated the inequality, but also for the exclusion of other potentially infeasible solutions.

In both cases, we build upon the structure of the inequality to be strengthened, as described in Proposition 1. In particular, the subset of arcs giving rise to inequality (18) represents a sequence of incompatible subpaths that are connected through consistency arcs. Preserving this structure is essential to ensure the validity of the resulting inequalities. Therefore, it is important that the strengthening process leaves the endpoints of each subpath unchanged. In other words, the first and last vertex of each subpath must remain fixed throughout the strengthening process.

Lifted inequalities

The following two families of inequalities are extensions of the *tournament constraints* proposed by Ascheuer et al. [3] for the Asymmetric Traveling Salesman Problem with Time Windows, adapted here to the ConTSP2.

We begin by introducing the necessary notation to define the strengthened inequalities. For a path $P = (v_1, \dots, v_r)$, we define the set of forward arcs as:

$$\Delta^+(P) := \{(v_i, v_j) \in A \mid 1 \leq i < j \leq r\}.$$

Proposition 2. *Let \mathcal{T} denote the collection of subpaths extracted from the support of an optimal solution to the dual verifier model $D(\tilde{x})$, where \tilde{x} is an infeasible solution to the ConTSP2. Then, the following inequality is valid for the ConTSP2 and represents a strengthening of inequality (18):*

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} x(\Delta^+(P)) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1. \quad (20)$$

Proof. The result follows by extending the argument presented in Lemma 4.1 of Ascheuer et al. [3] from a single path to a collection of subpaths. The inequality enforces that, for each subpath $P = (v_1, \dots, v_r) \in \mathcal{T}$, no complete traversal is allowed under a feasible solution to the ConTSP2, since such traversal would contradict the infeasibility of \tilde{x} .

Assume, for contradiction, that the inequality does not hold, i.e.,

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} x(\Delta^+(P)) > \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1.$$

Then, due to the degree constraints (2), each path $P \in \mathcal{T}$ must be fully traversed. That is, for $P = (v_1, \dots, v_r)$, we would have $x_{v_i v_{i+1}} = 1$ for all $i = 1, \dots, r - 1$.

This implies that all arcs within each $P \in \mathcal{T}$ are active in \tilde{x} , effectively completing each subpath. However, by Proposition 1, the presence of these subpaths in \tilde{x} is precisely what renders the solution infeasible, due to the formation of a consistency cycle.

Thus, such full traversal contradicts the assumption of feasibility, which establishes that inequality (20) is indeed valid and strictly enforced under infeasibility. \square

To further enhance the strength of these inequalities, we now consider a more general arc structure. Given a path $P = (v_1, \dots, v_r)$ with $r \geq 3$, let $S := \{v_i \mid 2 \leq i \leq r - 1\}$ denote the set of intermediate vertices. We define the arc set:

$$\Delta^\phi(P) := A(v_1 : S) \cup A(S) \cup A(S : v_r) \cup \{(v_1, v_r)\},$$

where $A(v_1 : S)$ includes all arcs from v_1 to nodes in S , $A(S)$ consists of all arcs between nodes in S , and $A(S : v_r)$ includes all arcs from nodes in S to v_r .

Let $t^*(P)$ denote the minimum travel time required to traverse from v_1 to v_r , visiting all nodes in S exactly once, that is, the length of the shortest Hamiltonian path from v_1 to v_r covering all intermediate nodes.

For any path $P \in \mathcal{T}$, we define $t(P) := \sum_{(i,j) \in P} t_{ij}$, i.e., the total travel time across the arcs in P . Extending this to the entire set \mathcal{T} , we let $t(\mathcal{T}) := \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} t(P)$. We also define $\omega(\mathcal{T}) := \sum_{(i,j) \in \bar{B}} \omega_c$, with $i = (c, k)$ and $j = (c, k')$, representing the sum of the maxTimeWidths associated with the consistency arcs in B that connect the subpaths in \mathcal{T} . When \mathcal{T} is derived from a solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}) \in D(\tilde{x})$, it holds that $t(\mathcal{T}) > \omega(\mathcal{T})$.

Proposition 3. *Let \mathcal{T} be the collection of subpaths extracted from the support of an optimal solution to the dual verifier model $D(\tilde{x})$, where \tilde{x} is an infeasible solution to the ConTSP2. If the following inequality holds:*

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} t^*(P) > \omega(\mathcal{T}), \tag{21}$$

then the strengthened inequality

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} x(\Delta^\phi(P)) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1 \tag{22}$$

is valid for the ConTSP2 and constitutes a tightening of inequality (20).

Proof. This result extends Theorem 4.5 in Ascheuer et al. [3] to the temporal consistency setting of the ConTSP2.

The violation condition (21) ensures that the total service time associated with the subpaths in \mathcal{T} exceeds the temporal flexibility allowed by the corresponding consistency windows. Moreover, this violation holds independently of the ordering of the internal tasks within each subpath.

Assume, for contradiction, that inequality (22) does not hold. Then, for each subpath $P = (v_1, \dots, v_r) \in \mathcal{T}$, the routing solution \tilde{x} would satisfy

$$x(A(v_1 : S)) = x(A(S : v_r)) = 1, \quad \text{and} \quad x(A(S)) = |S| - 1,$$

where $S = \{v_2, \dots, v_{r-1}\}$ denotes the set of internal vertices of P . This implies that every subpath $P \in \mathcal{T}$ is fully traversed in \tilde{x} .

Consequently, \tilde{x} would represent a feasible solution, which contradicts the assumption that it is infeasible. Therefore, inequality (22) must be valid under condition (21), thus completing the proof. \square

We now consider a hybrid form that combines the two types of inequalities described above.

Proposition 4. *Let \mathcal{T} denote the collection of subpaths extracted from the support of an optimal solution to the dual verifier model $D(\tilde{x})$, where \tilde{x} is an infeasible solution to the ConTSP2. Let \mathcal{T}_1 and \mathcal{T}_2 be a partition of \mathcal{T} such that:*

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_1} t(P) + \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_2} t^*(P) > \omega(\mathcal{T}). \quad (23)$$

Then, the following inequality is valid for the ConTSP2 and constitutes a further strengthening of (20):

$$\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_1} x(\Delta^+(P)) + \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_2} x(\Delta^\phi(P)) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1. \quad (24)$$

Proof. This proposition extends the previous strengthening by allowing hybrid compositions of subpaths: some with exact sequences and others whose internal vertices may be freely permuted, yet the resulting configuration still violates the problem's temporal consistency requirements.

The validity condition (23) ensures that the total service time required to traverse the subpaths in \mathcal{T} , considering durations $t(P)$ for paths in \mathcal{T}_1 and $t^*(P)$ for those in \mathcal{T}_2 , exceeds the maximum allowable time as established by the consistency windows. As in the previous case, this violation holds regardless of the internal task orderings in \mathcal{T}_2 .

Assume, by contradiction, that inequality (24) does not hold. Then, for each $P \in \mathcal{T}_1$, all internal arcs from the subpath would be active in \tilde{x} (i.e., $x(\Delta^+(P)) = |P|$), and similarly, for each $P \in \mathcal{T}_2$, all entry and internal arcs would be present (i.e., $x(\Delta^\phi(P)) = |P|$), implying the full realization of all paths in \mathcal{T} .

This would render \tilde{x} a feasible solution, contradicting the assumption of infeasibility. Hence, inequality (24) must be valid. \square

This final hybrid option proves particularly useful for strengthening inequality (20) in cases where condition (21) cannot be satisfied.

Figure 5 illustrates the lifting process applied to the example inequality (19). Subfigure 5(a) shows the application of Δ^+ , while subfigure 5(b) depicts the arc set Δ^ϕ .

Minimum infeasible subsystems

While the dual verifier model $D(\tilde{x})$ identifies a cycle of maximal violation, typically composed of several connected subpaths, this cycle is not necessarily minimal. That is, the infeasibility of the solution \tilde{x} may also be certified by a shorter sequence of arcs. Identifying such smaller subsets, or *minimum infeasible subsystems*,

(a) Lifting Δ^+ applied to example (19).

(b) Lifting Δ^ϕ for the same example.

Figure 5: Lifting process applied to the example inequality (19).

is useful for deriving tighter, more targeted cuts that exclude a broader set of infeasible solutions with fewer constraints.

To this end, once a violating solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ is obtained, one can conduct a secondary search for smaller infeasible substructures within the larger cycle. These reduced sequences still correspond to valid inequalities for the ConTSP2 but may be computationally more efficient and stronger in practice.

For example, in Figure 3, rather than considering the entire cycle connecting tasks $(c_{14}, 3)$ and $(c_{14}, 2)$, a smaller cycle involving tasks $(c_5, 3)$ and $(c_5, 2)$ can also be extracted. Although this cycle contains fewer arcs, it remains infeasible and yields a valid inequality. The corresponding constraint,

$$x_{(c_5,3),(c_4,3)} + x_{(c_4,3),(c_{14},3)} + x_{(c_{14},2),(c_{12},2)} + x_{(c_{12},2),(c_5,2)} \leq 3,$$

which contains as consistency arcs $((c_{14}, 3), (c_{14}, 2))$ and $((c_5, 2), (c_5, 3))$, eliminates any solution containing this shorter infeasible subpath combination.

Both the identification of minimum infeasible subsystems and the application of lifting offer a promising direction for refining the separation procedure and improving the overall strength and efficiency of the exact algorithm.

In summary, the proposed methodology leverages the structural presence of precedence constraints and arrival-time consistency constraints, which, in the case of the ConTSP2, are clearly delineated and isolated. This clarity enables a systematic identification of mutually incompatible subpaths whose combination defines a consistency cycle, revealing the source of infeasibility. Crucially, this combinatorial pattern can still be discerned even when these synchronization constraints are embedded within more complex vehicle routing problems that incorporate additional requirements, such as capacity constraints, heterogeneous vehicle fleets, or multi-depot structures. Recognizing this structure not only allows for the derivation of valid inequalities, but also supports the design of effective strengthening techniques to accelerate branch-and-cut convergence. As long as infeasibility arises from violations of these core synchronization mechanisms, the dual-driven path elimination framework remains broadly applicable.

6. Algorithm details

This section presents specific implementation details of the exact algorithm based on the path elimination model for solving the ConTSP2. These include the separation algorithms, constraint strengthening techniques, and the heuristic used to compute an initial feasible solution. While tailored here to the ConTSP2, most of the implementation components are standard and broadly applicable to any VRP-IATC.

The model (2)–(5), (9), (24), i.e., the path elimination model for the ConTSP2, includes an exponential number of constraints. To solve it exactly, we adopt a branch-and-cut approach, a standard method for handling such formulations. As described in Section 1.2, this technique combines branch-and-bound for exploring the solution tree with dynamic constraint generation to iteratively strengthen bounds. The effectiveness of this strategy largely depends on the quality of the LP relaxation bounds and the efficiency of the associated separation routines.

A notable advantage of the proposed technique lies in its simplicity and ease of implementation. Its application is immediate and requires only two core components: the separation of iPECs, achieved via a LP, and the strengthening of the resulting inequalities using straightforward, generic procedures. Additional elements, such as initial solution generation, are optional.

We rely on the default settings of the MILP solver for branching variable selection and node exploration. The LP solved at the root node corresponds to the LP relaxation of model (2), (3), (5), and (9).

6.1. Separation algorithms

During the constraint generation phase, we analyze a fractional solution \tilde{x} and execute a sequence of separation routines to identify violated cuts. Each round allows for the addition of up to 100 cuts per constraint family. A given separation procedure is invoked only if the preceding one fails to detect any violations. The subsections below describe the separation algorithms associated with each family of exponential constraints, in the order in which they are applied.

Connectivity constraints

Connectivity constraints (4) are separated using classical techniques (see, e.g., Fischetti et al. [18]). For each graph $G[k]$, with $k \in K$, we construct a capacitated network by assigning capacity \tilde{x}_{ij} to each arc $(i, j) \in A[k]$.

Then, for every node $i \in V'[k]$, we compute a minimum-capacity cut between the depot node $(0, k)$ and node i . If the cut capacity is strictly less than one, the associated subset S defines a violated connectivity constraint. Before running this check, we evaluate the number of connected components in $G[k]$; if more than one is detected, the corresponding connectivity constraints (4) for each component are added immediately.

The separation procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1, under the function `SEPARATECONN(\mathcal{R})`. This function takes as input the current constraint set \mathcal{R} at a given node of the branch-and-bound tree and returns an updated version of \mathcal{R} , enriched with new inequalities that eliminate any subtours found on each service day. Given a fractional solution \tilde{x} , obtained by solving the current LP relaxation, the violated connectivity cuts are identified through the method described above and added to the subset \mathcal{R}_{co} . The procedure iterates until no further subtours are detected in the current solution.

Infeasible path inequalities and strengthening

To identify violations of the strengthened infeasible path inequalities (24) (which generalize constraints (20) and (22)), we first detect violated consistency cycles using the method described in Section 5. For a given fractional solution \tilde{x} , we solve the dual verifier problem $D(\tilde{x})$ to obtain a pair $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$. If the dual objective value is negative, the solution reveals a violated consistency cycle. We then apply a depth-first search (Depth First Search (DFS)) to extract the structure of a violated cycle, which is used to construct the corresponding inequality (24).

This procedure is implemented in Algorithm 2 under the function IDENTIFYCYCLE(\tilde{x}). The function takes as input a candidate solution \tilde{x} and returns a set of subpaths \mathcal{T} , which correspond to the trajectory fragments extracted from the dual problem $D(\tilde{x})$.

As discussed in Section 5.3, any nonzero dual solution $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ defines a consistency cycle. To derive stronger inequalities, we search for smaller subsets within the same cycle that still define valid infeasibility cuts. This involves systematically identifying and evaluating all subsequences of subpaths that may satisfy the strengthening condition.

The next step consists of finding a partition of \mathcal{T} into two disjoint subsets, \mathcal{T}_1 and \mathcal{T}_2 , such that the validity condition (23) is satisfied. This partition is identified via exhaustive search by evaluating all possible combinations of subpaths. If a valid partition is found, a strengthened inequality of the form (24) is generated. Note that if \mathcal{T}_2 is empty, the resulting inequality reduces to form (20); similarly, if \mathcal{T}_1 is empty, it reduces to (22).

This final step is implemented in the function IDENTIFYIPEC, also described in Algorithm 2. The function takes the set of subpaths \mathcal{T} as input and returns a set of inequalities \mathcal{C} , which correspond to the iPECs generated from the partitioning process.

The overall separation procedure for iPECs is carried out by the function SEPARATEIPEC in Algorithm 2. This function takes as input the current constraint set \mathcal{R} and returns an updated set \mathcal{R}_{ip} , which includes the new iPECs derived from the candidate solution \tilde{x} . Note that this process is not applied iteratively, since the separation of iPECs requires the current solution to already satisfy the connectivity constraints (4).

Algorithm 1 Separation process for connectivity constraints.

```

1: function SEPARATECONN( $\mathcal{R}$ ) ▷ Returns ( $\mathcal{R}_{co}$ )
2:    $\mathcal{R}_{co} \leftarrow \mathcal{R}$ 
3:   repeat
4:      $\tilde{x} \leftarrow \text{SOLVE}(\min_{x \in \mathcal{R}_{co}} d^t x)$ 
5:      $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \text{IDEINTIFYCONNECTIVITY}(\tilde{x})$ 
6:      $\mathcal{R}_{co} \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_{co} \cup \mathcal{C}$ 
7:   until  $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ 
8:   return  $\mathcal{R}_{co}$ 
9: end function

```

Finally, the overall separation procedure performed during the bounding phase at a given node is outlined in Algorithm 3. This algorithm iteratively applies both connectivity and iPECs separation until no further

Algorithm 2 Separation process for infeasible path elimination constraints.

```

1: function IDENTIFYCYCLE( $\tilde{x}$ ) ▷ Returns ( $\mathcal{T}$ )
2:    $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta}) \leftarrow \text{SOLVE}(D(\tilde{x}))$ 
3:    $\tilde{A} \leftarrow \{(i, j) \in A \mid \tilde{\alpha}_{ij} > 0\}$ 
4:    $\tilde{B} \leftarrow \{(i, j) \in B \mid \tilde{\beta}_{ij} > 0\}$ 
5:    $\mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{GETSUBPATHS}(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B})$ 
6:   return  $\mathcal{T}$ 
7: end function
8:
9: function IDENTIFYIPEC( $\mathcal{T}$ ) ▷ Returns ( $\mathcal{C}$ )
10:  find a partition  $\mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2$  of  $\mathcal{T}$  such that  $\sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_1} t(P) + \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_2} t^*(P) > \omega(\mathcal{T})$ 
11:   $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_1} x(\Delta^+(P)) + \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}_2} x(\Delta^\phi(P)) \leq \sum_{P \in \mathcal{T}} |P| - 1$ 
12:  return  $\mathcal{C}$ 
13: end function
14:
15: function SEPARATEIPEC( $\mathcal{R}$ ) ▷ Returns ( $\mathcal{R}_{ip}$ )
16:   $\tilde{x} \leftarrow \text{SOLVE}(\min_{x \in \mathcal{R}} d^t x)$ 
17:   $\mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{IDENTIFYCYCLE}(\tilde{x})$ 
18:   $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \text{IDENTIFYIPEC}(\mathcal{T})$ 
19:   $\mathcal{R}_{ip} \leftarrow \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{C}$ 
20:  return  $\mathcal{R}_{ip}$ 
21: end function

```

violations are detected. At each iteration, the set of constraints \mathcal{R}' is updated with any newly identified inequalities. Once the iterative process concludes, the solution \tilde{x} obtained in the final execution of the SEPARATEIPEC routine is used to compute the dual bound z^* for the current search node, using the expression $z^* = d^t \tilde{x}$.

Algorithm 3 Global separation process.

```

1: function SEPARATION( $\mathcal{R}$ ) ▷ Returns ( $\mathcal{R}'$ )
2:    $\mathcal{R}' \leftarrow \mathcal{R}$ 
3:    $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4:   repeat
5:      $\mathcal{R}_{co} \leftarrow \text{SEPARATECONN}(\mathcal{R}')$ 
6:      $\mathcal{R}_{ip} \leftarrow \text{SEPARATEIPEC}(\mathcal{R}_{co})$ 
7:      $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \mathcal{R}' \setminus \mathcal{R}_{ip}$ 
8:      $\mathcal{R}' \leftarrow \mathcal{R}_{ip}$ 
9:   until  $\mathcal{C} = \emptyset$ 
10:  return  $\mathcal{R}'$ 
11: end function

```

6.2. Initial heuristic

A good initial upper bound can accelerate convergence by enabling earlier pruning in the branch-and-bound process. We implemented two complementary strategies to construct such bounds.

The first follows a template-based approach inspired by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41]. A TSP solution over all customers in C is computed and used to define a global precedence structure. Each daily route adheres to this structure, ensuring that the arrival-time consistency constraints for customer visits are satisfied (though not necessarily the overall route duration constraint).

The second strategy solves a series of TSPs, one per service day, each incorporating a precedence pattern updated from the previous iteration. This sequential refinement ensures consistency across days. Both approaches guarantee satisfaction of the consistency constraints for repeated customer visits but may violate time constraints at the depot.

For the first strategy, we use the nearest neighbor and cheapest insertion heuristics, followed by 2-opt local search. When no further improvement is observed, diversification is triggered and the best solution is retained. This procedure is repeated for a fixed number of iterations.

The second strategy requires solving multiple instances of the Precedence Constrained Traveling Salesperson Problem (PC-TSP), for which we use a custom MILP model. As in the main algorithm, path elimination constraints enforce precedence compliance. A simple constructive heuristic provides initial solutions to help guide the solver. Each instance is limited to 30 seconds, resulting in a worst-case time of 150 seconds for five service days.

Results from both strategies are reported in Tables 3 and 4 (see Section 7). For each instance, we report the total solution time, root node gap, and time spent solving heuristic subproblems. These metrics allow us to assess the relative impact of the heuristic phase on overall computational performance.

7. Computational results

The computational study presented in this section pursues a dual objective. First, it aims to validate the design of the proposed dual-driven path elimination methodology by comparing the three formulations introduced in Section 4, evaluating their effectiveness and quantifying the performance improvements resulting from the integration of iPEC-based reasoning. Second, it seeks to provide experimental evidence that the dual-driven approach, when embedded within a branch-and-cut framework for solving the ConTSP2, is not only effective but also competitive with, and in some respects superior to, the best-performing exact algorithm currently available in the literature.

To this end, we begin by comparing the performance of the three aforementioned formulations: a baseline compact model that uses arrival-time variables, a strengthened variant that augments this model with connectivity constraints, and a third formulation based on infeasible path elimination constraints, which entirely avoids the use of arrival-time variables. This comparison reveals the impact of structural reinforcement and illustrates the advantages of enforcing temporal consistency through routing-based cuts. We then contrast the performance of the most effective of these models, the Path Elimination formulation, with that of the decomposition-based method proposed by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41], which remains the current state of the art for solving the ConTSP2.

All implementations were developed in C++ and compiled with gcc version 13.3.0 on a Linux Ubuntu 24.04 LTS system using the `-O2` optimization flag. Experiments were run in single-threaded mode on an Intel Core i5-7500 processor with 20 GB of RAM. CPLEX 22.1, accessed through its callable library, was employed to solve the branch-and-cut formulations, with a time limit of 7,200 seconds per instance, in line with the computational settings adopted in Subramanyam and Gounaris [41]. The implementation relies primarily on embedding direct replicas of Algorithm 3 within CPLEX’s callback mechanisms. In particular, the procedure is invoked through the `LazyConstraintCallbackI` and `UserCutCallbackI` classes, used respectively to separate feasibility cuts and to generate valid inequalities that strengthen the LP relaxation. In addition, the same routine is called within the `IncumbentCallbackI` to validate candidate integer solutions; whenever a violated cut is identified, the incumbent solution is discarded.

To provide an immediate perspective on the scope of the experiments and the effectiveness of the proposed approach, we open this section with a concise summary of the main computational outcomes. Table 2 reports the aggregated performance of the main algorithms considered in this study. For each method, it presents the number of benchmark instances solved to proven optimality and the corresponding average runtime, together with the number of unsolved instances and their mean residual optimality gap. The results reveal a clear progression from the SEC-enhanced formulation to the dual-driven path elimination model, which solves the largest number of instances within the shortest average time. For reference, the aggregate results reported by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] are also included.

The remainder of this section is organized as follows. Section 7.1 describes the benchmark instance sets and summarizes their main characteristics. Section 7.2 presents a preliminary comparison among the three proposed formulations, highlighting the advantages of the path elimination model. Section 7.3 contrasts the results of this model with those reported by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41], the best-performing exact

Table 2: Aggregated computational performance of the main proposed algorithms. For each method, the table reports the number of benchmark instances (out of 756) solved to proven optimality (#) and their average runtime (seconds), as well as the number of unsolved instances (out of 756) and their mean residual gap (%). Results reported by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] are included for reference.

<i>Method</i>	<i>Proven optimal</i>		<i>Residual gap</i>	
	<i>#</i>	<i>t(sec)</i>	<i>#</i>	<i>% gap</i>
Proposed algorithms ^a				
SEC-Enhanced	401	469.3	355	1.4
Path elimination	536	381.8	220	1.6
Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] ^b	524	492.1	232	2.8

^aIntel Core i5-7500 CPU @ 3.40GHz.

^bIntel Xeon @ 2.80GHz family.

method for the ConTSP2. This part includes both a methodological comparison between the two approaches and a concise performance assessment, which reinforces the contribution of our dual-driven strategy in terms of simplicity and ease of implementation. Finally, Section 7.4 provides details on the availability of the complete datasets and results generated by the proposed algorithms.

7.1. Test instances

To evaluate our algorithm, we used the two ConTSP benchmark sets proposed in Subramanyam and Gounaris [40, 41]. The first set is based on the 23 TSPLIB instances (Reinelt [34]) with up to 51 nodes, which were extended into three- and five-period versions of the ConTSP. Each instance is defined by two parameters: (a) the probability $f \in 0.5, 0.7, 0.9$ that a customer requires service in a given period, and (b) the value ω for customers in C' , set at 10%, 15%, or 20% of the maximum (across periods) travel time of the corresponding optimal single-period traveling salesman tours. Each original TSPLIB instance was thus transformed into nine three-period and nine five-period ConTSP instances, yielding a total of 414 instances. In these instances, travel costs and travel times coincide, but they are not necessarily symmetric or hold with the triangle inequality.

The second set considers 342 instances following the same procedure described in Kovacs et al. [27] and Subramanyam and Gounaris [40], applied to all TSPLIB instances with up to 101 nodes. These instances were also extended into three- and five-period versions of the ConTSP.

Subramanyam and Gounaris have defined a value for the duration limit ω_0 . They have set ω_0 to 1.1 times the maximum (across periods) travel time of the corresponding optimal single-period TSP tours.

With the experimental setup defined and the benchmark instances introduced, we now proceed to evaluate the performance of the proposed solution strategy. We begin by comparing the three algorithmic implementations described above, focusing on their behavior across different instance families.

7.2. Evaluation of the proposed implementations

The three formulations presented in Section 4 reflect different modeling philosophies: the Compact model emphasizes simplicity and ease of implementation; the SEC-Enhanced model incorporates classical

structural reinforcements; and the Path Elimination model leverages problem-specific infeasibility cuts based on incompatible subpaths. Unlike the first two models, which explicitly encode synchronization constraints via arrival-time variables, the Path Elimination formulation avoids these variables altogether, embedding feasibility through structurally derived cuts.

To assess their relative performance, we conducted a preliminary computational study on a representative subset of instances. All three models, Compact, SEC-Enhanced, and Path Elimination, were implemented and solved using an identical MILP solver configuration.

The results exhibit a clear performance gradient. The Compact formulation performed poorly even on small- and medium-sized instances, primarily due to the weak LP relaxation induced by big- M constraints. Adding connectivity constraints in the SEC-Enhanced model significantly improved both bounds and solution times. Finally, the Path Elimination formulation consistently outperformed both alternatives, producing tighter bounds and faster convergence, thanks to the integration of strong, problem-specific infeasibility cuts.

Table 3 summarizes this initial evaluation. It reports the performance of the three implementations across 42 instance families. Due to the poor performance of the Compact formulation, we report its results only for the first 23 families (the first 414 instances).

The main goal of this study is to assess the impact of reinforcing the Compact model with connectivity constraints and replacing synchronization constraints (expressed via arrival-time variables) with subpath elimination cuts. While these enhancements compromise the structural compactness of the model, they substantially improve the number of instances solved to optimality, the root node relaxation quality, and the overall solution time.

Table 3 is organized into three main blocks, each corresponding to one of the evaluated implementations. For each block, we report the following four performance indicators:

- $r(\%)$: average root node gap, calculated as $\frac{ub-lb}{ub} \times 100$, where lb and ub are the lower and upper bounds after root node processing;
- $\#$: number of instances solved to optimality (out of 18) within each family;
- $t(sec)$: average solution time (in seconds) for solved instances;
- $g(\%)$: average optimality gap for unsolved instances at termination.

The first two columns of the table provide additional context:

- *Instance*: name of each instance family;
- $h(sec)$: average running time (in seconds) of the initial heuristic for that family.

The impact of connectivity constraints on the Compact model is particularly notable, even though they are not required for feasibility. These constraints act as strong reinforcements of the LP relaxation. While the Compact formulation alone solves only 184 of the first 414 instances, its connectivity-enhanced counterpart solves 325, and does so with an average time of 566 seconds, compared to the 988 seconds required by the

original formulation to solve half as many. The average root gap also improves significantly, from 10.7% in the Compact model to just 1.4% in the SEC-Enhanced version, confirming the value of connectivity as a relaxation strengthening mechanism.

The Path Elimination implementation clearly outperforms both alternatives. It solves all 18 instances in 16 of the 42 families and achieves global optimality for 536 of the 756 benchmark instances. Notably, 15 of these 16 families involve relatively small instances with 13-41 customers. However, the approach fails to solve any instances in two large families with 69 and 75 customers, respectively. Despite this, the Path Elimination model exhibits superior runtime performance, even when compared to the SEC-Enhanced formulation, which appears faster only in cases where it solves fewer instances.

The performance gap between the SEC-Enhanced and Path Elimination models is evident as early as the first 15 instance families: the latter solves all of them, while the former succeeds with only nine. In many cases, solution times for the SEC-Enhanced model exceed those of the Path Elimination model by an order of magnitude. In the few rows where the SEC-Enhanced version appears faster, it corresponds to instances it failed to solve. Overall, across the 42 instance families, the SEC-Enhanced model solves 131 fewer instances and, on average, requires over 20% more time than the Path Elimination model on those it does solve.

A more detailed analysis focused exclusively on the SEC-Enhanced and Path Elimination models, disaggregated by instance parameters, is presented in Table 4. This table also aims to experimentally assess the impact of replacing arrival-time variables and their associated consistency constraints with infeasible path elimination constraints. The results are grouped according to key characteristics such as the number of customers (n), the number of delivery tasks (m), the number of service periods ($|K|$), and two instance-generation parameters: the fraction parameter f and the width of ω (see Subsection 7.1).

The columns of the table are defined as follows:

- *Parameters*: description of each parameter group, including the number of customers n , delivery tasks m , service periods $|K|$, the fraction parameter f , and the width of ω ;
- h (*sec*): average runtime (in seconds) of the initial heuristic for instances in the group;
- $\#ins$: number of instances in the parameter group.

For each of the two algorithms implementing the SEC-Enhanced and Path Elimination models, the following performance indicators are reported:

- $\#sol$: number of instances solved to optimality within the group;
- r (%): average root node gap, computed as $\frac{ub-lb}{ub} \times 100$;
- t (*sec*): average runtime (in seconds) for solved instances;
- $\#nod$: average number of branch-and-bound nodes explored (for solved instances);
- $\#conn$: average number of connectivity cuts added during the solution process (for solved instances);
- $\#ipec$: (*Path Elimination model only*) average number of infeasible path elimination constraints added (for solved instances);

Table 3: Performance comparison of three exact implementations for solving the ConTSP2, grouped by instance family.

Instance	$h(sec)$	Compact ^a				SEC-Enhanced				Path elimination			
		$r(\%)$	#	$t(sec)$	$g(\%)$	$r(\%)$	#	$t(sec)$	$g(\%)$	$r(\%)$	#	$t(sec)$	$g(\%)$
burma14	0.5	11.1	16	201.5	2.0	0.6	18	0.2	-	0.6	18	0.1	-
ulysses16	0.8	11.3	12	744.0	3.9	0.9	18	0.6	-	0.8	18	0.2	-
br17	0.2	45.2	15	90.8	2.3	0.0	18	0.0	-	0.0	18	0.0	-
gr17	1.4	8.1	16	755.0	0.6	0.6	18	3.2	-	0.6	18	0.4	-
gr21	0.6	0.4	18	0.5	-	0.1	18	0.1	-	0.1	18	0.0	-
ulysses22	0.7	13.3	3	2,289.6	5.5	0.1	18	0.4	-	0.1	18	0.1	-
gr24	1.2	2.7	18	191.5	-	0.4	18	194.7	-	0.5	18	12.0	-
fri26	1.3	5.9	12	711.3	1.6	1.1	17	680.5	0.2	1.0	18	14.9	-
bayg29	2.2	3.5	12	289.4	0.8	0.4	18	4.9	-	0.5	18	0.5	-
bays29	1.8	3.4	15	491.4	0.8	0.3	18	16.6	-	0.3	18	1.3	-
ftv33	2.2	6.1	13	1,060.4	2.1	3.3	14	182.2	1.1	2.5	18	330.8	-
ftv35	2.6	6.1	8	1,826.4	1.9	3.6	14	985.5	1.6	3.2	18	429.8	-
ftv38	4.3	4.6	9	974.3	2.1	2.8	11	663.0	1.5	2.2	18	1,427.1	-
dantzig42	12.9	11.5	0	-	6.9	1.2	16	570.2	0.2	1.2	18	34.0	-
swiss42	7.6	5.9	6	1,493.7	0.9	1.5	15	847.0	0.7	1.4	18	158.9	-
p43	39.6	64.7	0	-	9.0	0.1	6	60.1	0.1	0.1	9	653.2	0.0
ftv44	4.7	5.9	0	-	2.3	3.7	7	2,641.9	1.7	3.2	9	108.5	1.3
att48	12.1	9.3	0	-	5.1	1.3	10	957.5	0.9	1.4	16	151.8	0.3
ftv47	7.5	4.3	3	397.8	2.3	3.0	9	513.0	2.6	2.6	12	664.5	1.4
gr48	18.0	5.5	5	2,771.7	2.3	1.1	12	644.4	0.6	1.1	14	77.9	0.5
hk48	15.8	5.5	0	-	1.8	1.4	12	1,083.2	0.9	1.6	14	87.7	0.5
ry48p	17.9	8.0	0	-	3.7	1.7	14	1,082.0	0.8	1.3	17	39.9	0.7
eil51	15.2	4.6	3	2,498.1	1.8	2.5	6	1,884.1	1.2	2.2	11	1,193.5	1.2
<i>Aggr. Inst. 1 - 414</i>	7.4	10.7	184	987.5	2.8	1.4	325	565.9	1.0	1.2	372	234.2	0.8
berlin52	40.5					0.5	14	347.3	0.3	0.5	18	23.4	-
ft53	49.6					2.7	3	814.5	1.1	2.2	13	232.1	1.9
ftv55	16.4					3.2	8	116.0	1.9	2.6	12	217.4	3.2
brazil58	33.3					0.1	17	28.3	0.2	0.2	17	1.8	0.0
ftv64	54.7					3.8	3	64.4	2.4	3.1	5	2,035.9	1.4
ft70	211.0					4.1	0	-	3.0	4.1	0	-	3.8
st70	36.9					1.2	7	105.5	0.6	1.2	12	272.2	0.7
ftv70	51.4					4.1	0	-	2.4	3.4	5	2,440.0	2.3
eil76	75.5					2.9	0	-	2.2	2.7	3	1,541.7	2.2
pr76	198.4					3.0	0	-	1.9	2.9	0	-	1.9
gr96	162.5					2.0	0	-	0.9	1.7	9	1,333.4	1.0
rat99	178.2					2.2	1	6,207.0	1.4	2.3	7	2,217.6	1.6
kroA100	105.3					1.6	3	61.0	0.8	1.0	10	1,194.5	0.7
kroB100	148.1					1.8	3	1,312.2	1.3	1.6	5	1,523.2	1.1
kroC100	142.1					1.2	5	1,195.9	0.5	0.9	14	1,063.9	0.1
kroD100	96.0					1.1	3	4,894.0	0.4	1.0	11	910.7	0.2
kroE100	154.3					1.7	1	606.7	0.9	1.6	7	717.2	1.0
rd100	137.9					1.6	5	1,002.3	1.2	1.6	10	449.4	1.1
eil101	154.5					2.3	3	227.6	1.6	2.2	6	1,668.5	2.1
<i>Aggr. Inst. 1 - 756</i>	52.8					1.7	401	469.3	1.4	1.6	536	381.8	1.6

^aOnly the first 23 families.

- g (%): average optimality gap at termination for unsolved instances, computed as $\frac{ub^* - lb^*}{ub^*} \times 100$.

A final block of the table, titled *Improvement*, summarizes the impact of replacing arrival-time variables with infeasible path elimination constraints, reporting the increase in the number of instances solved and the average reduction in root node gap.

A close examination of Table 4 reveals several noteworthy patterns regarding how the performance of both algorithms is influenced by different instance characteristics, and highlights the superiority of the Path Elimination model over the SEC-Enhanced approach.

As expected, problem size, measured by the number of customers (n), has a major impact on tractability in both cases. All instances with $n \leq 20$ are solved to optimality by the SEC-Enhanced algorithm, and the Path Elimination model maintains full success up to this same threshold. However, the success rate steadily declines as n increases, dropping sharply for $n > 60$. This decrease in solvability is accompanied by a significant increase in computational effort: larger instances require longer runtimes, explore more branch-and-bound nodes, and generate more cutting planes.

A similar trend is observed with respect to the number of delivery tasks (m): nearly all instances with $m \leq 100$ are efficiently solved by the Path Elimination algorithm, whereas performance deteriorates for larger values in both solution rate and computational efficiency. Nevertheless, the termination gaps for unsolved instances remain relatively small, indicating that the algorithm continues to provide high-quality dual bounds even when optimality is not reached within the time limit.

The number of service periods ($|K|$) also affects performance. Both algorithms exhibit the same qualitative behavior in this regard, differing primarily in the number of instances solved. Problems with three periods are consistently easier to solve than those with five, which demand similar computational effort but result in fewer optimal solutions.

Regarding the instance-generation parameters, higher values of the fraction parameter f , which lead to denser delivery schedules, appear to facilitate the solution process. In particular, instances with $f = 0.9$ exhibit the lowest average root node and termination gaps for both algorithms. Finally, the results show that algorithmic performance remains stable across different values of ω , suggesting that the Path Elimination model is robust to variations in arrival-time flexibility.

The last block of Table 4 summarizes the impact of replacing arrival-time variables with infeasible path elimination constraints. The Path Elimination model consistently outperforms the SEC-Enhanced formulation, yielding lower average root node gaps that translate into marked improvements in the number of instances solved across all parameter settings.

In addition, we provide two *performance profiles* in the sense of Dolan and Moré [15], which offer an intuitive visualization of relative performance across the benchmark set. These plots depict, for each algorithm, the proportion of instances it solves within a given factor of the best observed performance. As such, performance profiles provide a robust and widely accepted framework for comparing the efficiency of optimization algorithms over diverse problem instances.

Figure 6 displays the profiles of the three proposed algorithms on the reduced set of 414 instances (to allow the inclusion of the compact model), while Figure 7 compares the SEC-Enhanced and Dual-driven

Table 4: Average computational performance of the implementation of the SEC-Enhanced and Path elimination model as a function of benchmark characteristics

Parameters	SEC-Enhanced						Path elimination						Improvement				
	$h(sec)$	#ins	#sol	$r(\%)$	$t(sec)$	#nod	#conn	$g(\%)$	#sol	$r(\%)$	$t(sec)$	#nod	#conn	#ipec	$g(\%)$	#sol	$r(\%)$
$n \in (0, 20]$	0.7	90	90	0.4	0.8	1,379	49	-	90	0.4	0.1	94	46	45	-	0	0.01
$n \in (20, 40]$	2.0	144	128	1.5	305.5	115,839	299	1.4	144	1.3	277.1	35,521	286	591	-	16	0.21
$n \in (40, 60]$	20.8	252	149	1.7	743.4	209,621	593	1.1	198	1.6	216.8	31,612	470	1,045	1.2	49	0.16
$n \in (60, 80]$	104.6	108	10	3.2	93.2	16,742	415	2.2	25	2.9	1,210.8	90,325	954	1,789	2.2	15	0.26
$n \in (80, 100]$	142.1	162	24	1.7	1,553.7	93,806	877	1.0	79	1.6	1,158.5	98,861	1,117	674	1.1	55	0.19
$m \in (0, 100]$	2.8	261	245	1.1	202.3	87,234	260	0.8	258	1.0	90.4	14,974	188	384	0.1	13	0.12
$m \in (100, 200]$	35.6	288	132	2.1	703.9	181,414	552	1.5	205	1.9	473.3	52,879	591	1,122	1.8	73	0.16
$m \in (200, 300]$	85.9	138	21	2.1	1,985.5	153,848	786	1.3	64	1.9	998.8	89,861	996	906	1.7	43	0.22
$m \in (300, 400]$	195.5	42	0	2.1	-	-	-	1.3	2	1.8	1,505.5	129,736	1,239	469	1.3	2	0.25
$m \in (400, 500]$	328.3	27	3	1.3	1,331.1	18,040	1,049	0.9	7	0.9	2,479.8	105,228	2,099	858	0.7	4	0.39
Three-period	25.5	378	237	1.6	412.1	103,262	403	1.1	321	1.5	379.8	39,332	475	673	1.4	84	0.18
Five-period	80.1	378	164	1.8	551.9	147,139	371	1.6	215	1.7	384.7	41,047	456	828	1.6	51	0.17
$f = 0.5$	44.8	252	154	2.0	433.6	134,449	376	1.7	188	1.8	255.1	35,535	346	677	1.9	34	0.12
$f = 0.7$	41.1	252	114	2.0	369.5	136,421	399	1.6	167	1.9	564.3	54,314	539	905	1.8	53	0.17
$f = 0.9$	72.4	252	133	1.2	596.0	92,832	398	0.9	181	1.0	345.0	31,489	527	639	0.9	48	0.22
Low ω	54.0	252	127	1.8	444.0	122,503	384	1.4	173	1.6	489.5	50,499	499	817	1.5	46	0.20
Med. ω	52.6	252	135	1.7	578.4	143,779	408	1.4	178	1.6	287.3	35,503	447	688	1.5	43	0.17
High ω	51.8	252	139	1.7	386.4	98,099	377	1.3	185	1.5	372.0	34,566	458	703	1.6	46	0.15

path elimination formulations on the complete set of 756 instances. These profiles are consistent with the aggregated picture in Table 2, providing additional evidence of the competitive performance of the path-elimination model.

Figure 6 illustrates the superior performance of the Path Elimination model compared to the other two proposed algorithms. As reflected in both the plot and Table 3, the Dual-Driven Path Elimination algorithm solves 89% of the first group of 414 instances, outperforming its competitors also in terms of speed (i.e., for smaller values of τ). The SEC-Enhanced model, while significantly improving upon the baseline compact formulation, still lags behind the path-based approach, solving 78% of the instances. In contrast, the Compact model exhibits substantially lower performance, solving only 44% of the instances and generally requiring longer computation times.

Figure 7 confirms the same performance pattern when comparing the SEC-Enhanced and Path Elimination models over the full benchmark set. However, the inclusion of 342 additional, larger instances leads to a proportional decrease in the percentage of solved cases for both models.

Figure 6: Dolan–Moré performance profiles of the three proposed algorithms over the reduced set of 414 instances. The horizontal axis represents the performance ratio τ , while the vertical axis indicates the fraction of instances solved within τ times the best performance.

7.3. Benchmarking against the state of the art

The most effective exact algorithm currently available for solving the ConTSP2 is the one proposed by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41], which follows a decomposition based framework, as previously discussed in Subsection 1.2. Their algorithm is capable of solving not only the problem addressed in this work (the ConTSP2), but also its variant that disallows idle times (the ConTSP1).

Figure 7: Dolan–Moré performance profiles comparing the SEC-Enhanced and Dual-Driven Path Elimination formulations over the complete set of 756 instances. The horizontal axis represents the performance ratio τ , while the vertical axis indicates the fraction of instances solved within τ times the best performance.

Since Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] do not report experimental results specifically for the ConTSP2, a direct performance comparison between their approach and the one proposed in this paper is not feasible. For this reason, we provide two complementary types of comparison: a methodological analysis and a performance evaluation. The objective is to establish a common reference framework that allows us to assess the contributions of each approach in a consistent manner.

Methodological analysis

We next provide a comparative description of the algorithm by Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] and the one proposed in this work, highlighting both methodological differences and the complexity of their core procedures. Both methods follow a branch-and-bound framework but differ fundamentally in their decomposition scheme: Subramanyam and Gounaris rely on time-window disjunctions, whereas our approach employs a classical arc-based strategy. Figures 8 and 9 illustrate these differences.

Figure 8 shows the flowchart of a generic branch-and-bound algorithm. The comparison focuses on the three procedures highlighted in blue, *Initialize*, *Process node*, and *Branching*, which represent the main points of divergence. We place particular emphasis on the *Process node* step, as it entails the greatest differences in computational complexity.

While the variables x leading to a solution \tilde{x} have already been defined in Section 4 for the algorithm proposed in this paper, we assume that the variables used in our representation of the Subramanyam and Gounaris method carry a similar interpretation. In the flowchart of Figure 9, we denote by $\tilde{x}[k]$ the values of the subset of variables associated exclusively with the arcs of period k , for each $k \in K$.

Figure 8: General branch-and-bound framework shared by both algorithms. The highlighted procedures (*Initialize*, *Process node*, and *Branching*) are the main points of divergence.

Figure 9: Detailed comparison of the procedures highlighted in Figure 8. The left column lists the main procedures, while gray entries denote selected subprocedures of *Process node*.

Each branching node ν is characterized by common attributes: $\nu.\text{fathom}$, indicating whether the node is infeasible after processing; $\nu.\tilde{x}$, the primal solution if feasible; $\nu.\text{feasible}$, specifying whether $\nu.\tilde{x}$ satisfies all CTSP2 constraints. Its lower bound is computed as $z^* = d^t \nu.\tilde{x}$.

The *Initialize* procedure constructs the root node ν^0 and inserts it into the list of unexplored nodes \mathcal{N} . The algorithm then iteratively extracts nodes from \mathcal{N} , processes them, and either discards them, updates the incumbent, or branches further.

Figure 9 details the three highlighted procedures for both algorithms. In the Subramanyam and Gounaris method, each node ν includes additional attributes: $\nu.\tau$ (branching time windows τ_c for each $c \in C$), which underpin the decomposition scheme; $\nu.\tilde{w}$, which stores a time window \tilde{w}_c for each $c \in C'$, computed from the arrival times of solution $\nu.\tilde{x}$ and the time windows specified by $\nu.\tau$, where each $\nu.\tilde{w}_c = [\underline{w}_c, \bar{w}_c]$ represents the minimum and maximum arrival times associated with c ; and $\nu.w^*$, which records the maximum difference $\bar{w}_c - \underline{w}_c$ over all $c \in C'$. In our path elimination approach, each node instead contains $\nu.\mathcal{R}$, the linear model associated with it.

The key difference in *Initialize* lies in the construction of the root node. Subramanyam and Gounaris start from fully relaxed time windows $[0, \omega_0]$ for each $c \in C$ and progressively refine them through branching, guided by embedded TSPTW subproblems solved with the algorithm of Ascheuer et al. [4]. By contrast, our method builds the root node from the basic model (2)–(9), with relaxed integrality constraints, and applies arc-based branching.

In the *Process node* procedure, the Subramanyam and Gounaris method solves $|K|$ TSPTW subproblems (one per period), each requiring a branch-and-cut tree and advanced constraint separation (connectivity constraints [12], blossom inequalities [2], π -, σ -, and (π, σ) -inequalities [5], and path elimination constraints [3]). Although effective, this step is computationally demanding: the authors report that 80% of the runtime is consumed by fewer than 10% of these subproblems, with some several hundred times slower than the median. To mitigate this, they include a fallback mechanism: if a TSPTW subproblem exceeds a time limit, the search backtracks and explores alternative disjunctions precomputed at the node.

In contrast, our method applies only polynomial-time separation routines, as described in Section 6.1 (Algorithms 1–3), resulting in a much lighter *Process node* step. Thus, while the Subramanyam and Gounaris method solves $|K|$ NP-hard problems, ours performs polynomial separation, trading stronger bounds for greater simplicity.

Feasibility checks also differ. Subramanyam and Gounaris discard a node if any $\tilde{x}[k]$ is empty (i.e., no feasible solution to a TSPTW subproblem). They also verify global CTSP2 feasibility by solving a linear program (COMPUTETW) that computes arrival times minimizing the maximum difference $\bar{w}_c - \underline{w}_c$ and updates $\nu.\tilde{w}$ and $\nu.w^*$. A solution is feasible if $\nu.w^* \leq \omega$. By contrast, our method simply checks whether the model after separation is feasible and whether $\nu.\tilde{x}$ is integral.

Finally, branching strategies diverge. Subramanyam and Gounaris branch on the time window of the customer $c^* \in C'$ with the largest $\bar{w}_c - \underline{w}_c$, combining this with initial heuristics and warm-starts for embedded subproblems. In contrast, our algorithm employs straightforward arc fixation: selecting a fractional variable x_{ij}^k and generating two child nodes with $x_{ij}^k = 0$ and $x_{ij}^k = 1$.

It should be noted that, although the substantial difference in computational complexity between the

core procedures of the two algorithms has been emphasized in favor of the method proposed in this work, the number of nodes explored by the Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] algorithm is considerably smaller. This is because the information obtained by solving each embedded TSPTW subproblem enables more restrictive and informed branching decisions than those achievable through simple arc fixation. Therefore, while their approach incurs a much higher per-node computational cost, the quality of the branching decisions compensates for this overhead, resulting in a significantly smaller number of nodes explored overall.

Performance comparison

Although Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] do not provide detailed results for each of the 756 benchmark instances, beyond reporting optimal or best-known values, Table 3 of their paper presents an aggregate summary. Their method solves 524 out of 756 instances within a two-hour time limit, with an average runtime of 492.1 seconds, 566.8 nodes explored on average, and a mean optimality gap of 2.81% for the unsolved cases. A key strength of their approach is its applicability to both problem variants, ConTSP1 and ConTSP2, which explains why most of their results are reported in aggregate form.

As previously mentioned, our experiments were conducted in single-threaded mode on an Intel Core i5-7500 CPU @ 3.40GHz (2016), whereas Subramanyam and Gounaris [41] report using an Intel Xeon @ 2.80GHz. Based on the publication date, we assume this corresponds to the Xeon E5-2680 v2 (2013). According to PassMark benchmark data,⁶ the i5-7500 achieves a single-thread score of 2,253 versus 1,791 for the Xeon, i.e., about 20% higher single-core performance. Comparisons of computational times should therefore be interpreted with caution.

Within this context, Table 3 shows that our path elimination algorithm solves 536 instances to optimality (12 more than the decomposition method of Subramanyam and Gounaris [41]) and identifies 35 new best-known solutions.⁷ The average runtime for these 536 instances is 381.8 seconds, substantially lower than the 492.1 seconds reported for their 524 solved instances. This gain in speed comes at a cost: our algorithm explores an average of 39,934 nodes, compared to only 566.8 nodes in their study. Note, however, that their figure excludes the additional nodes generated within each embedded TSPTW subproblem.

The decomposition algorithm clearly benefits from tighter bounds obtained during node processing. By solving TSPTW subproblems, their method produces more restrictive and informed branching decisions than those available under arc fixation. Recall that they branch on the position and width of time windows.

Thus, the two approaches embody fundamentally different branching philosophies: arc-based branching versus time-window-based branching. The former follows a standard implementation, while the latter constitutes a novel idea requiring an embedded TSPTW solver and tailored primal heuristics. The strength of the path elimination algorithm lies in its simplicity: it only requires separating connectivity and path elimination constraints, leaving all remaining decisions to a standard MILP solver.

While hardware differences prevent a definitive comparison in absolute terms, the results nonetheless highlight the competitiveness of our approach. Despite relying on simpler mechanisms, the proposed method achieves comparable performance in terms of solution count, runtime, and discovery of new best-known

⁶<https://www.cpubenchmark.net/compare/2910vs2061/Intel-i5-7500-vs-Intel-Xeon-E5-2680-v2>

⁷https://github.com/RieraULL/CTSP2_results/blob/main/output/Path-elimination/Summary_Path_Elimination.csv

solutions. These findings suggest that, in practice, algorithmic simplicity can yield strong performance when coupled with effective cut-generation strategies.

7.4. *Reproducibility and data availability*

To support transparency, benchmarking, and future research, we have made available a comprehensive repository containing all computational results⁸. This open-access resource includes complete instance-level data: the nature and parameters of each instance, execution metrics such as solving times, optimal or best-known solutions, lower and upper bounds (when available), number of explored nodes, and detailed cut statistics by type. Full CPLEX log files are also provided. Beyond simply reporting summary statistics, this repository enables in-depth analysis and direct comparison with future algorithms, facilitating reproducibility and establishing a solid baseline for future contributions to the study of the ConTSP2.

8. Conclusions

This paper presents a simple and generalizable technique for solving vehicle routing problems with operation synchronization, particularly those involving idle times and arrival-time consistency. The approach is applicable to problem settings where the underlying structure allows the feasibility subproblem to be formulated as a linear program, and the objective function does not depend on arrival or waiting times. Under these conditions, the method exploits the combinatorial structure revealed by a dual verifier model to generate infeasible path elimination constraints and to strengthen them systematically through general-purpose procedures.

The approach is easy to implement, requiring only the solution of a basic linear program and a straightforward strengthening step.

We applied the technique to the ConTSP2, a problem that captures the essential structural features required by our framework. Computational experiments show that the method is highly effective, solving instances with up to 100 customers over five service days to proven optimality, and achieving performance comparable to the best algorithms reported in the literature.

To encourage reproducibility and facilitate future comparisons, all computational results, including raw data and solver logs for each instance, are publicly available in a dedicated GitHub repository. We hope this resource will serve as a solid foundation for the development and evaluation of future exact and heuristic methods for the ConTSP2.

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⁸https://github.com/RieraULL/CTSP2_results

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to improve the clarity, style, and linguistic accuracy of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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